

D5.5

Report on Awareness Raising Activities

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-ROLES tasks

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Task 7.3	Pairing visits

GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HR	Human Resources
IGOT	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
WLB	Work-Life Balance
WP	Work Package
YW	Yellow Window

Executive Summary

This document is the Report on Awareness Raising Activities (D5.5) developed under task 5.4 by WP5 leader UDEUSTO. Once a complete set of training modules have been designed in D5.4 and are in the process of being implemented, this document contains the outcomes of the different formative activities. These training modules targets different audiences in order to fulfil the WP objectives, which have primarily to do with the achievement of a more gender-balanced leadership bodies in GEP implementing institutions and with giving all the involved people some tools to enhance the skills and the awareness-raising regarding leadership and decision-making.

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1. Introduction

This document is the *Report on Awareness Raising Activities (D5.5)* by WP5 leader University of Deusto.

The general objectives of the WP are focused on two main areas:

- (i) encourage equal participation of men and women in leadership and decision-making structures, and
- (ii) support awareness raising through the development of behavioral changes to promote an inclusive leadership.

In order to achieve these objectives, several initiatives have been developed around leadership and gender-balanced decision-making processes, in accordance with the main issues identified in the [Institutional Assessment Reports](#) (see D5.4 for further clarification). As the final step of the process, this report intends to reflect the main outcomes from each of the initiatives and how these activities contributed to the WP's objectives.

This report is divided into three different sections. Each section corresponds to one of the three actions planned. In the first section, the outcomes from the different workshops delivered in the Pairing Events are described. These sessions aim to produce general learnings and take-home messages for both the members of the task forces and the leaders of the institutions that took part in the session (which are, in fact, the main target stakeholders for these trainings).

The second section includes information derived from the online webinars. The project planned to hold specific sessions for each of the implementing institutions, so each webinar was partner specific. However, in the case of the webinar chaired by YW in partnership with GE-Academy Project held on the first semester of Year 2, general conclusions applicable to all the partners will be highlighted, as well as specific learnings that emerged from the sharing of experiences.

The third and final section of this report will capture the outcomes from the Two-Day Leadership Programme (which was targeted at female middle managers within the GEP implementing partners), in particular, whether the particular objectives of the programme were achieved or whether further work is required.

Finally, it is important to highlight that, as scheduled in D5.4, most of the trainings were performed during the second year of the project, with the exception of the workshops delivered at the Pairing Events. Therefore, this deliverable will not be able to offer a complete view of all of the set of actions planned, as there are still ongoing initiatives.

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2. Outcomes from the Workshops in the context of Pairing Events

In this section, the most relevant findings from the workshops delivered at each of the Pairing Events by the leader of WP5 are highlighted. These sessions tried to achieve a double objective. The first objective was to deliver training about certain specific topics affecting leadership, in particular, in HEIs (see D5.4 for a description of each training session). The second objective, was aimed at delivering a reflection and teamwork session to raise awareness about the specific topic/problem tackled and how specific institutions and their leaders participating in the workshop could make improvements in that area.

The target audience of these workshops were the current leaders of the GEP implementers, who were invited to the Institutional Pairing Events by their own institutions. These sessions allow leaders to exchange common challenges and concerns, similarities and differences in relation to gender issues in leadership among institutions, as well as the strategies that each of them is developing and the problems they are facing. The dialogue between them invites them to feel involved in the implementation of GEPs, in particular on the issue of gender issues in leadership, which is where they are more influential. In order to have a more fluent conversation, we restricted the sessions to the participants.

2.1. Session 1: General Overview of Gender in Leadership

The first session of the leadership workshops took place in the Pairing Event that was hosted by OBU in M6. The session was attended by:

Position	Institution	Sex
VR for Academic Community	UDEUSTO	Male
Dean of Business School	UDEUSTO	Male
WP5 Coordinator	UDEUSTO	Female
Project Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Scientific Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Dean of Faculty of Arts	UL FF	Male
Vice-Dean of Faculty of Arts	UL FF	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	UL FF	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	UL FF	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	OBU	Female

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GEARING Core Group Member	OBU	Female
Associate Dean for Research and Knowledge Exchange	OBU	Female
HR Manager	OBU	Female
Senior Lecturer	OBU	Female
Research Assistant	OBU	Female

This session was mainly directed to decision makers from implementing partners, aimed at raising awareness about gender discrimination at work. This workshop put together ideas and experiences from the different participating partners with a general overview of the consequences of women’s limited representation in leadership. In particular, we covered different areas: Gender in management, communication, Work-Life Balance (WLB), salary wages and other rewards, cultural values and leaders’ awareness about gender issues in leadership. The slides used during this presentation can be found under Annex 1.

Among others, gender and leader stereotypes were described, with a particular focus on the so-called “think manager-think male” theoretical perspective in social sciences to understand gender issues in management, underscoring its effects for women advancement and the mismatch between female and leader stereotypes (gender-leader role incongruity).

The WLB section tackled specific questions about the domestic division of labor and remaining challenges around childcare and domestic responsibilities of women compared to men. The other topics mentioned above were described in a broader way, setting the necessary background to promote reflection among the participating partners around the issue of “*Why are so few women in top management positions?*” as a backdrop to all of them.

The last part of the workshop was devoted to encouraging the participating leaders to reflect on why they were involved in the session and to critically think about their relevant role as agents for change. To finish the session, the teams of each institution reflected upon where their own organization was positioned regarding the different areas discussed during the session. Afterwards, these findings were shared with the entire group to find common challenges and take-home messages. For this purpose, each team was provided with a template, in which they could write down their reflections and the positioning of the institution. This template can be found under Annex 2.

The exercise allowed a critical reflection about biased self-evaluations and remaining challenges within each dimension of gender equality. An analysis of the main findings per category is

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provided below. In relation to the culture of the organization, OBU and UL situated themselves in the middle of the scale (2 out of 4 points), whereas UDEUSTO team rated itself as 3.5 points.

In the field of awareness, **UDEUSTO** again rated itself higher than the other two institutions (3.5 versus 3 and 2.4 points of **UL** and **OBU** respectively), which means the team considers **UDEUSTO** to be doing a lot in terms of raising awareness about gender in leadership issues.

Communication affecting women to achieve leadership positions was rated as a 1 out of 4 by **UL**, a 2 for **UDEUSTO** and a 3.5 for **OBU**. In this case, what appears to be a weakness for some institutions is a strength for others.

Work-life balance is considered more positively by OBU, with a 0.5-point difference for **UDEUSTO** and 1-point difference for **UL**. Salary appears to be the strongest area of OBU, rating themselves with the maximum score, while **OBU** and **UDEUSTO** rated themselves as 3 and 2.5 respectively.

Finally, when considering gender in management, the relevant distinction between the sex and gender dimensions was covered, asking participants to reflect about the level of development of both women (i.e., sex dimension) and communal values and principles (i.e., gender) in leadership. **OBU** attributed relatively high scores to both dimensions (2.8 vs 3 for gender and sex respectively), whereas for instance **UDEUSTO** made this differentiation on the opposite direction (they rated UDEUSTO as higher –score 3 out of 4- in the development of communal values than advancement of women – score 2 out of 4). **UL** rated both of them equally (2 points out of 4).

As a general conclusion, participants realized that **UDEUSTO** and **UL** share communication as their biggest challenge, while **OBU** considers culture as their major area of improvement. On the contrary, **OBU** considers salary and rewards as its main strengths; **UL** salary and awareness; and **UDEUSTO** awareness, and culture.

It is important to highlight the fact that these scores were merely created for reflection purposes and based only on participants' opinions, which means that they should also be contrasted and compared with the data shown in the Institutional Assessment Reports to determine whether these personal views are supported within the institution. However, this exercise was a good starting point to make the participants reflect on how gender is embedded in different areas at their institutions and was rated very positively by participants.

2.2. Session 2: Flows of Decision-Making in GEP implementing partners

The second session took place during the Pairing Event in IGOT-UL in M11. In this session, WP5 leader worked with the partners involved in the flows of decision-making in higher education institutions.

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Position	Institution	Sex
HR Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Dean of Social and Human Sciences Faculty	UDEUSTO	Male
WP5 Coordinator	UDEUSTO	Male
Project Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Scientific Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Director of CEG	IGOT	Male
Dean of IGOT	IGOT	Male
Executive Director	IGOT	Male
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Male
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	IGOT	Female
Dean of Business School and Pro-Vice Chancellor	OBU	Male
HR Manager	OBU	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	OBU	Female
GEARING Core Group Member	OBU	Female

The aim was to provide some basic notes regarding the importance of having decision-making processes that do not create barriers for the advancement of women in HEIs and research

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institutions. In this sense, the topics that were covered include the different types of decision-making processes (structured vs. unstructured), the gender biases included in these processes and the consequences. The slides can be found as Annex 3.

Then, to put all the concepts into practice, the different teams were asked to design and share with the group a typical decision-making process of a Dean's appointment in their institution (or any top management position in the case of RFOs), putting particular emphasis on the biases that each phase of the process may encounter. The template used for this purpose can be found under Annex 4.

Delving deeper into the outcomes of the workshop it is necessary to address two different topics: the decision-making process itself and the potential biases that can emerge in its different stages.

In the case of **IGOT-UL**, the process is well defined, with clear stages and procedures that are mandatory to follow in order to appoint a Dean. It is important to state that all the processes are described in national regulations, as it is a public entity. Therefore, the influence of institutional leaders on these procedures is limited. Regarding the potential biases IGOT's team identified, they are mainly related to the gender-composition of the personnel at their institution. In particular, in the stages involving the electoral commission and school council, the lack of regulations ensuring gender parity in the composition of the commissions and the representation of teaching staff were identified as the main risks of biases within the selection process. Along with these two, the last potential bias is linked to candidates. Indeed, every candidate aspiring to a Dean position has to be full professor of IGOT, the small share of women in that position has a general impact in the process.

In the case of **Oxford Brookes University**, they have identified several biases in the selection process. It is worth noting that the process is seen as a general hiring process, as it is not a requirement to belong to the institution to be appointed as a Dean (with the associated position of Vice-Chancellor).

During the first stages of the process, affinity bias and a "recruit-rather-than-change" bias may appear, especially in the stage of reviewing role requirements. During the call for applicants, the language and the pictures used, the way the university and/or faculty is positioned, as well as the network and the affinity bias of the head-hunter, may determine the number and kind of candidates step forward.

During the selection process, two different bodies are involved. One individual body, the Recruitment Manager or Chair (who, for the final decision, is accompanied by a Vice-Chancellor) and one collective body, the selection panels. The bias that could potentially emerge are different according to the body. In the case of the Recruitment Manager and VC, personal bias may be involved (either when choosing the criteria to be used during the process or the

components of the panel for the next stage). The influence of the chair and formal authorities should also be considered.

Finally, in the case of the phases of the process involving a panel, groupthink and over-emphasis of some criteria (which means giving more importance in the weighting when selecting a certain profile) were identified as the main biases, adding to the personal biases held by individual members of the panel, as outlined above.

The last participant in the workshop, **University of Deusto**, started its reflection by differentiating between the formal process (the one contained in the general statutes of the institution) and the informal activities. These informal activities mainly consist of informal conversations between Rector and faculty members prior to the beginning of the process to gather as many opinions as possible about potential candidates. In these informal conversations, principal biases may appear related to the type of questions asked and the lack of structure of the interview. Furthermore, the impossibility of spontaneous candidature could also be considered as a risk of bias in the process.

The formal process starts with the submission of 1-3 potential candidates to the Faculty council by the Rector. Here, personal biases of the Rector are the most influential ones, as well as the tendency of reducing the submission to a single candidate, which limits the opinion of the next participants in the process. Following on from this, a consultation process begins with a questionnaire that has to be filled in by the members of the Faculty council and several meetings are held with the Faculty council and the Board of Directors to discuss these. During these three events, the potential biases identified are related to the questions included in the questionnaire, the limited knowledge both the Faculty council and the Board of Directors may have on the candidates and the general perception about the usefulness of the meetings (consultative vs. binding process).

The final decision about the appointment is in hands of the Governing Council, upon the Rector's proposal. In this stage, the composition of the council (mainly male and senior profiles) and the lack of knowledge about the candidates are the main biases which were identified. As a conclusion, the team participating in the workshop stated that the general feeling in the institution is that most of the process is in the Rector's hands, and that the consulting stages are not binding enough to repel some candidates (or to find more).

2.3. Online Pairing Event: Gender Stereotypes and Leadership Styles

The third session was intended to be held in M18 in the context of the Institutional Pairing Event in Ljubljana. However, due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, this session was postponed until physical Pairing Events were possible. Given that several Pairing Events were postponed, it was decided to deliver an online Pairing Event, in which leaders from all six GEPIS took part in order to discuss challenges around leadership and decision-making. In this event, an introductory session and two workshops were delivered by WP5 coordination: one on gender

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stereotypes and another one about leadership styles (see details below). To end up the session, GEARING-Roles coordination closed the session and an evaluation of the activities was made.

The online pairing event, organized by UDEUSTO team and delivered on 29.03.2021, confirmed the participation of 17 leaders:

Position	Institution	Sex
Head of International Research Project Office	UDEUSTO	Female
Vice-Dean of International Relations – Law Faculty	UDEUSTO	Male
General Manager of Deusto Business School Executive Education	UDEUSTO	Female
WP5 Coordinator	UDEUSTO	Female
Project Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Scientific Manager	UDEUSTO	Female
Dean of IGOT	IGOT	Male
Executive Director	IGOT	Female
Vice-President	IGOT	Female
Vice-President	IGOT	Male
Senior Lecturer in Human Resources Management - Coaching & Mentoring	OBU	Female
Assistant Director Social Science Research for the Institute for Ethical AI	OBU	Female
Executive Director	ETAg	Female
Head of Department of International Research Cooperation	ETAg	Female

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Head of the Estonian Liaison Office for EU RTD in Brussels	ETAg	Female
Human Resources Director	SABANCI	Female
Public Relations Director	SABANCI	Female
Chief Financial Officer	SABANCI	Female
Head of Department of Sociology	UL FF	Male
Associate Dean of Undergraduate Studies - 1st Cycle, Postgraduate Studies - 2nd Cycle, and Information Systems	UL FF	Female
Associate Dean of Doctoral Studies - 3rd Cycle and Research	UL FF	Male

The pairing event started with an introduction by WP5 coordinator about the results of the survey conducted in all GEPIs regarding leadership and decision-making processes (see Deliverable 5.2) in order to give leaders more information about current state of affairs on their institutions. Then, an open debate with leaders of UDEUSTO, IGOT and ETAg (as the leaders originally planned to attend the visit) was carried out, facilitated by Maxime Forest (YW).

IGOT representatives acknowledged the importance of all the thinking generated by GEARING-Roles, and the need for time to achieve balanced decision-making bodies. They recognised that there is still gender bias on the institution, with feminized faculties but male-dominated research teams.

Furthermore, **ETAg**, as a research funding organization, expanded this knowledge by helping other public institutions and universities to develop its own GEPs, and fostering gender-balanced composition of evaluation panels in a more systematic way.

To finish the session, **UDEUSTO** stressed that Ignatian values were highly compatible with more open and horizontal and sensitive ways of exerting leadership, which could be seen as a potential area of alignment between their core institutional values and the principles of gender equality and more communal styles of leadership. Real challenge and opportunity to illustrate into practice more gender sensitive, also in terms of numbers, to show that those are living values, not only an inspiration.

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After a break, the first workshop was held by WP5 coordination. The aim of the session was to reflect around gender stereotypes as one of the factors contributing to the barriers in the access of women to leadership positions (Heilman et al, 1995). The session tried to give light to the different stereotypes that contribute to the so-called gender-role incongruity that describes how a mismatch between the gender-type of a role and the gender stereotype associated with a given individual based on their sex contributes to gendered outcomes (Eagly and Karau, 2002).

This topic was subsequently approached by means of a participatory technique called Lotus Blossom (designed by Yellow Window). In the middle of the template, several pictures representing a stereotypical (but still present) situation were shared with the participants. These vignettes are coming from the work that GEARING-Roles is currently developing around Gender and Humor, gathering humoristic vignettes to counteract sexist humor and facilitate discussion in project activities. This *Humorarium* is a work in progress lead by the Deusto and YW teams in Gearing Roles and up to date has collected over 60 feminist cartoons. The aim of this work is to foster the use of feminist humor as a counter argument to sexist humor in academic environments, but also to provide visual resources to different project activities. The sample has been collected through an internet search. All the cartoons have been categorized according to different criteria, including topic, source and sex/gender of the authors

In breakout sessions, they were asked to reflect, first, about the issues each vignette suggest to them and, second, about the possible solutions to that specific situations.

Participants were divided into three subgroups to facilitate the development of the activity. On each of the subgroups, a different EU vignette was presented.

The first group reflected around the following vignette:

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There, participants made a great number of observations and comments around the picture. In particular, they reflected on the imbalance of power the image represents, with a board of directors without any single women on it. They concluded that a diversity target should be pursued, by revising their hiring and promotion policies, as there are discriminatory practices on them.

Moreover, they focused on the clothing policies, stating that whenever there is a man who is the leader, we do not pay attention to their appearance, but when the manager is a woman, we are paying attention to her clothes. This issue comes from early age education, when women are educated just to look forward to have these positions.

Finally, several other topics arose in the debate, such as the space and power, calling for the need to renovate old structures (big table and everybody around it) to modern spaces; the act

vs. talk, where leaders hold meetings but they did not end them with concrete actions to implement; or the feminine versus feminist dichotomy.

In the second group, the picture for reflection shows a woman who is not integrated in the discussion during the meeting, she is being ignored by the rest of the members (all men):

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They identified several reasons for this behavior. This kind of formal relations always depend on informal communication, where men talk about *men issues* among them, leaving woman out of the conversation, as it is difficult for her to be part of it. The situation of being ignored, she is used to it. Letting it go. This is something that many women on this position have experienced. To be the only female in these meetings.

As possible actions to be implemented, they have a clear one in mind: have a balanced number of women and men in these meetings. They underscored how in situations in which women are not alone at the table they will grow their self-confidence. They argued that a culture of trust and confidence may be even more efficient than the quota, because some women can get the impression that through a quota they are not recognized by their merits. Gender and relation of power should be at the same level of importance.

Facilitator asked whether this self-confidence idea is a more individual change or it should come from the organizational culture and the organizational level. Participants responded that this should come from the institution. Changing coming from the institution improves the level of trust and cooperation among people. And the confidence of women could improve.

The last subgroup reflected around stereotypes and biases in HR processes with the following picture:

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The debate revolved around how women are expected to take care of these types of roles and responsibilities. They concluded that women take these responsibilities because they are also biased with caring responsibilities and motherhood responsibilities. As a consequence, they experience great difficulties when they achieve management positions to balance this biased view of the care work with the responsibilities they must develop in their professional role.

Furthermore, this group get deeper in this issue and asked themselves how the laws and the policies do help in overcoming or mitigating these types of biases and sharing the responsibilities among men and women. They believe that it is a process to dismantle the bias with these types of policies. Maternity leave can be a big problem, because the structural approach to this issue is not taken into consideration. They concluded that, in order to be effective, maternity and paternity leaves need to be taken by both parents. However, how this is taken into consideration and how this is a solution or not is discussed.

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Finally, they highlighted the difference between public and private institutions, as in the group were participants from both types of GEPIs. The regulation applicable to them is different, so they may need to take different type of policies.

The session ended with a plenary discussion, in which each of the groups shared with the others their reflections around these vignettes.

The last workshop was devoted to leadership styles that are perceived in our institutions and the different outcomes that can be achieved when facing a similar situation with different styles.

The session started with a brief presentation by Leire Gartzia (WP5 coordinator), in which she explained that leadership styles are important influences not only for organisational effectiveness (Yukl, 2010), but also for gender equality. Furthermore, to a great extent the interest in women as leaders has traditionally focused on whether they lead in a more communal (i.e., people oriented) way than men, consistent with “female advantage” proposals (Eagly, Gartzia & Carli, 2012).

Participants were asked to position themselves as a task or people-oriented leader and as a gender-aware or gender-neutral leader. Results show that, while task and people orientation were balanced (47% and 53% respectively), a vast majority of participants (93%) rate themselves as gender-aware.

Then, concepts were put into practice by developing a role-play activity. In that activity, participants were presented with a situation in which, as general managers, they must adopt a decision of reorganization of their departments that will mean reducing personnel, improve the decision-making processes and the economic viability. The leader should explain this decision to a staff representative.

To perform the activity, participants were divided into two subgroups. There, once the situation had been role-played by two volunteers, the rest of participants shared their views about the leadership styles that have been displayed in the simulation, as well as possible ways of improving it.

As in the previous session, once the activity ended all the participants got back to the plenary in order to share a final team reflection about how they have felt in that situation and the importance of paying attention to one’s style when leading a team.

Both subgroups shared common key messages arising from this activity. Firstly, they believe that a balance between a task-oriented and a people-oriented approach is very useful in situations as the one role-played. Some participants highlighted that they try to combine both styles in their roles, looking for the best both for the team and for the objectives of the institution.

Furthermore, negotiation is key for this kind of situation to ensure that everyone is happy with the decision. Finally, it is important to open a process of dialogue to take this kind of decisions.

This dialogue does not need to refer to “what to decide” but “how to decide”. That is to say, even when the decision is already taken, it is important to open space for a dialogue concerning the consequences of this decision for the different groups affected.

To close the session, several questions were shared with participants via Mentimeter in order to gather their opinion about the session. Some of the answers included:

What is the main lesson you learnt today?

Mentimeter

- Leader vs Manager it is not necessarily a gender issue
- Some insights into the specifics of the cultures within partners' organisations
- Exchanging on gender issues with other institutions going through the same changing process is very important to learn together and to rise awareness
- There are different perceptions regarding the need to incorporate the gender perspective in leadership. It is important to know how to communicate that gender inequality and diversity, although related, are not the same because women are the 50% of p
- Involving people at all levels of the organizations as it highlights ingrained beliefs and the justifications for these beliefs.
- We are in the same boat no matter where we are geographically

Which initiatives/suggestions made by other participants do you think you could apply in your own institution?

Mentimeter

- Not a specific action but a continuous work in this gender issue
- Leader vs manager it's not necessarily a gender issue
- it is important to highlight this topic and draw attention to the gender equality
- Still a long way to fight gender stereotypes in decision-making
- The difficulty of applying the quotas in the University. Place where the idea of excellence and meritocracy prevail as objective ideas
- it is important to not forget the importance of the issue

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3. Outcomes from the Online Webinars

As part of the GEARING ROLES project, four webinars were conducted. These responded to the needs identified by partners in the Institutional Assessments. Priority issues common to all institutions were: lack of awareness by senior management teams; resistances to implementation; and bias. Two webinars were closed, and two open for participants from outside the consortium. Consortium partners were asked to select one or two senior management leaders to participate in the webinar series (specifically the closed webinars 2 and 4). This section outlines the objectives and key discussions of each webinar.

3.1. First open webinar

The first open webinar was held on the 30th April 2020, 10.00-11.15 (CET).

This open webinar, organised in collaboration with and also promoted by GE-Academy sister project, was entitled *“Bias and resistances: exploring challenges to gender equality in leadership and decision-making”*. It was designed as an introductory session on bias and resistances for a range of audiences, including core groups of GEP implementers; equality officers; decision-makers; senior female leaders in higher education; and future female leaders in higher education. The objectives of this session were:

- Clarify the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making.
- Explore resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making.
- Discuss strategies for tackling bias and resistances.

The webinar included presentations by Maxime Forest and Lucy Ferguson, followed by open discussions on the key issues raised. The full webinar is available [here](#).

Maxime Forest’s presentation explored *“Why Gender Equality should matter to Meritocracy and Academic Excellence: tackling gender bias in decision-making and leadership”*. It covered issues such as: meritocracy and excellence; sticky floor, glass walls and glass ceiling; academic power

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structures and merit; and the reproduction of bias and inequality. The presentation closed by setting out the notion of “inclusive excellence”, and some proposed steps for tackling bias.

Following this, Lucy Ferguson presented on “How do we address resistances to achieving gender equality in leadership and decision-making?” She began with a quotation by Fiona McKay (Figure 1) and asked participants to discuss in the chat whether they agreed with the argument. She then outlined an approach to categorising resistances based on “why/how/who”. Participants then shared examples of resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making they have. The presentation closed with a discussion of why resistances matter and how they contribute to transformative change for gender equality.

Figure 1: Quotation by Fiona Mackay

The open discussion was lively and fruitful, with a large number of comments being shared in the chat. One participant pointed out that the images of women in work depicted white women, which led to a discussion around intersectionality in bias and leadership. Another participant pointed out the importance of addressing issues with the younger generation in terms of structural change for gender equality. Other issues included: why top leaders are often so reluctant to change; is recruiting more men to lower positions a sensible strategy for addressing the “sticky floor”? The discussion then centred around “thinking and working politically” to address patriarchal structures, vested interests and privilege in institutions. Participants asked about “gender fatigue” in the face of slow change and resistances to gender equality, and Ferguson discussed the importance of acknowledging the need for care work for core teams working on gender equality. She then outlined some key practical tools for addressing common resistances to gender equality.

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Apart from the organizers of the webinar, 76 people participated, spanning 22 countries. Out of these, 24 were from the GEARING ROLES consortium. Eight H2020 sister projects were also represented (SUPERA, GenderSMART, Baltic Gender, SPEAR, CALIPER, GEECCO, CASPER, GENDER ACTION AND GE-Academy). While senior managers from partner organizations were invited to participate, few did. As such, a further effort was made to ensure these people participated in the second webinar.

3.2. First closed webinar

The first closed webinar, for GEARING-roles' partners only, was held on the 12th June 2020, 10.00-11.15 (CET). The webinar was entitled *"Exploring Bias and Resistances to Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making in Partner Organizations"*.

This session was aimed at middle and senior managers in the partner institutions. Before the session, participants were asked to provide a definition of leadership, and to respond whether they thought their institution experiences bias and resistances in addressing gender equality in leadership. Of the 15 participants who registered, 5 said they did not believe there were bias and resistances in their institution.

Participants were informed that the webinar would be dedicated to free and open discussion of perceptions and examples of bias and resistances within partner institutions, and that these discussions would be confidential. They were asked to view the introductory webinar in advance, in order to familiarize themselves with the key concepts.

The objectives of the webinar were to:

- Identify bias in leadership and decision-making in partner organizations
- Identify resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making in partner organizations
- Explore strategies for tackling bias and resistances

The webinar used an interactive format to allow for maximum participation and discussion, within the limits of the online setting. A range of interactive tools were used - including polls, the collaborative Whiteboard, quizzes, the chat facility and breakout rooms - in order to stimulate discussion. Participants were asked to describe the qualities of a good leader; find an image of a "leader" online; and take a quiz on gender and leadership in research and innovation statistics across the EU. Overall, the participants were open and active, particularly in the small group discussions.

In terms of participation, 15 people took part in the webinar from the 6 partner institutions. Positions included: Dean, Vice Dean, Vice-Rector, Scientific Director, Executive Director, and Academic Affairs Coordinator.

The participants were split into two breakout rooms to discuss resistances to gender equality in their organizations, mixed between institutions. They discussed examples of resistances to

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increasing gender equality and leadership and decision-making in their organization. These included:

- The belief that equality has already been achieved
- The meritocracy discourse
- Resistances to go through an external evaluation or to show/share the results of the evaluation
- Unable to see gender imbalances or to consider them as a problem
- Perception that work is done with 60% women in workforce
- Lack of awareness (unconscious bias)
- In institutions, sometimes it is difficult to find women for certain positions in order to foster gender equality in different boards

Reasons given for why these resistances exist included:

- We want to incorporate the flag of equality (diversity) but without challenging previous structures (because we were supposed to be already very “progressive”)
- General resistance to change
- Institutional changes are difficult because they may challenge the typical hierarchy structure
- Not seeing the ‘business case’ and mainstream business improvement - especially in time of crisis
- Not enough awareness or knowledge of what gender equality really means and the benefits it entails for everyone in an organization (not just women)
- Old-fashioned beliefs
- We have too many priorities, worries, too much on our plate; and this comes down in the priority list
- Patriarchal ideology: belief that the claim is ideological
- Women leaders fear perception of tokenism and reduction in ‘quality’
- Middle-class and white liberal discourse - resistant to risk for non-typical progression routes /experience
- We believe we are fair!
- Requests for more and more and more DATA
- Gender equality and race/ethnicity action seen as separate - intersectional issues not understood

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- Gender fatigue - it is always the same people addressing these topics

Several suggestions were given for dealing with resistances:

- Show gender equality (as well as diversity management) as a benefit for the future of the whole organization
- Enable open discussion
- Delivery of Gender Equality Plans and regular assessment
- Importance of involving top-management leaders and to make them aware of the benefits of gender equality for the institution
- Changing socio-cultural values and beliefs, so more actions and discussions are needed
- Positive action for recognition of gender and other identities and experience
- Do not perpetuate care duties as female duties
- Gender mainstreaming is important to foster institutional change
- Apply the law of gender parity

The exit questionnaire was completed by 10 participants and feedback was overwhelmingly positive. Participants found most interesting the following aspects: new perspectives on the "resistances" issue; the active participation of the leaders of the participating universities; the focus on the concept "unconscious institutional bias"; and the different points of view and the different experiences.

In terms of the main points learned, these included: the importance of institutional bias in institutional practices; resistances and biases are very similar across institutions and countries; that it is possible to approach people resistant to gender training; putting in practice the theory of the first webinar, confirmation of some main hypothesis; and that gender bias is entrenched in HEI structures, practices and routines but can (and must) be dismantled through open discussion and carefully decision-making processes. Participants noted that the online format was used well, and they would like the opportunity to have more time to develop certain aspects of the issues covered in the webinar in other formats and spaces.

3.3. Second open webinar

The third session of the webinar series took place on the 30th September 2020, 10.00-11.15 (CET). The webinar was entitled "*Challenges for Feminist Leadership in Higher Education Institutions*".

This open webinar, organized in collaboration with and also promoted by GE-Academy, was designed to explore in more detail some of the challenges identified to date in the webinar series. The webinar was opened by Vasia Madesi (GE-Academy), followed by María López who introduced the GEARING ROLES project and the speaker. Professor Fiona MacKay from the

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University of Edinburgh was invited to reflect at length on some key dilemmas and challenges related to feminist leadership. The full webinar is available [here](#).

In addition to the organisers of the webinar, 66 people participated, spanning 26 countries (Afghanistan, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, India, Ireland, Malta, Morocco, Nigeria, North Macedonia, Pakistan, Peru, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sudan, Sweden, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and United States of America.) 20 participants were from the GEARING ROLES consortium, of whom 5 were from the FELISE mentorship programme. Seven H2020 sister projects were also represented (GE Academy, GEECCO, SUPERA, Gender-Smart, TRIGGER, EGERA, GRACE, and CALIPER). Participants represented a range of roles, including: Vice-Dean, Vicesecretary of Faculty, Member of the Pedagogical Board, EU Projects Administrator, Managing Director, Head of Pre Award, Senior Statistician, Head of Human Resources and Organisation, Entrepreneurship Director, and Head of Centre for Gender and Science. This represents a broader range of profiles than the first open webinar and reflects the increased recruiting efforts of the team.

Fiona's thirty-minute presentation was highly engaging, charting her own journey to being an "academic feminist manager". She explored four questions:

- What can feminists do when they take on management roles?
- How do feminists-who-manage experience simultaneously embodying institutional authority and oppositional knowledge?
- To what extent are there opportunities to work with the grain of an institution to challenge the gendered status quo from within?
- Are feminists-who-manage inevitably co-opted and compromised?

Fiona summarized her presentation with the following take-away points:

- Chipping Away
- Seizing the moment
- Recognising limits and divided loyalties
- Ongoing power of stereotypes
- Where do feminists and their allies need to be? Everywhere!

María López then provided some substantive comments on the presentation, which were followed by in-depth discussion from the participants. Some of the issues explored included:

- How can feministic leadership be executed without 2nd and 1st tier leadership positions and without an official gender equality policy in a university where women make up the majority?
- The importance of 'self-care' and mutual support among feminists.

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- The relationship with other feminist colleagues, and whether they demonstrate solidarity and support. At the same time, the possibility of Do you experience any confrontation with more “opportunistic” female leaders.
- How to prevent the depoliticization of feminist leadership principles once they enter institutions. Often, once these concepts enter institutions, they become aligned to the frameworks and agendas already driving that institution, and become diluted or codified, reduced to ‘competency frameworks’ and lose their teeth.
- How feminist leaders can position themselves and identify the roles and projects that they take on, in order to avoid as Fiona says becoming "responsible for everything".

In closing, participants expressed an urgent need for academic feminist leadership mentoring and networks or foundations.

From the 17 evaluation forms completed, all participants were satisfied with the webinar, in particular the presentation by Fiona MacKay.

3.4. Second closed webinar

This fourth and final webinar in the series, held on the 21st October 2020, 10.30-12.00 (CET), was a follow-up on the previous closed session entitled *“Exploring Challenges to Leadership in Research and Higher Education”*.

The same participants were invited. As before, participants were informed that the webinar would be dedicated to free and open discussion of how to tackle bias and resistances within partner institutions, and that these discussions would be confidential.

The objectives of the webinar were to:

- Discuss key issues and challenges for leaders in research and higher education institutions
- Explore the concept of “feminist leadership”
- Review leadership targets in a Gender Equality Plan

16 people participated in the webinar. 6 of these were from the UDEUSTO/Yellow Window team, leaving 10 senior managers across the six partner institutions - the majority of whom had attended the first closed webinar. Of these, 4 were senior male leaders, allowing for a mixture of perspectives on gender equality issues and gendered experiences of leadership.

The webinar began by reviewing the examples of resistances from the previous closed webinar. Participants were then invited to share a leadership challenge they had faced in their institution. A key discussion revolved around whether work-life balance is a challenge just for women leaders, or also for men. In addition, participants discussed how we can work towards new forms of leadership where we are encouraging working fewer hours and fewer meetings. It was

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suggested that we should be focusing on how we want to work and reconfiguring leadership for the future.

Following this, Leire Gartzia, WP5 coordinator, from UDEUSTO, presented on the concept of “feminist leadership”. Participants discussed whether they considered themselves to be a feminist leader, with a range of perspectives expressed. Some participants were more clearly in favour of incorporating the terms feminist than others, which served as an interesting starting point for the debate. Among others, the following ideas were shared:

“I have feminist leadership concerns but not yet there... this is a process and path with many obstacles along the way”

“Is it (only) a matter of leadership 'style'? Or also 'content'? Dealing with women's concerns and needs? Substantive representation of women in decision-making?”

“Feminist leadership is important. Women in power are necessary to achieve representativeness and diversity, but that does not guarantee feminist leadership.”

Among participants who were more openly against referring to themselves as “feminist leaders”, the following ideas were shared, among others:

“I said no because although I'm for equality it is not a priority at this moment”

“The modern world needs new leadership skills and styles. I am not sure should we call it feminist leadership. Maybe just say that female characteristics suit better for a new leadership style.”

“I tried to think more in terms of balanced representation... so I said I am not a feminist leader.”

“Is it maybe a matter of semantics? Not wanting the 'label'? Would 'inclusive leadership' be an alternative?”

“I will research more about the concept of feminist leadership. I avoid all isms in general.”

Following this discussion, María López presented the leadership and decision-making aspects of their GEP, and participants asked questions to clarify key issues.

Closing reflections included a discussion regarding the stigmatisation of the concept of feminism. For example, participants were asked what was the difference for them between being “for equality” and being a feminist leader? Responses included:

“We live in a world where most topics tend to be polarised very fast. Labelling leadership as feminist could also polarise and it seems to me it doesn't help to achieve our goals.”

“It remains a challenge to foreground the transformative aspects based on feminist principles - so the mention of inclusive practice, (self-) reflection and challenging status quo, advocating social justice and change. We also need to avoid the conflation which reinforces 'gendered' stereotypes' of behaviours - caring, compassion, empathy.”

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The exit questionnaire was completed by 5 participants and feedback was overwhelmingly positive regarding the format, content and delivery of the webinar. Participants found a range of aspects interesting, including the University of Deusto presentation; strong resistances to feminism; and Gartzia's questions and presentation on feminist leadership.

In terms of what they found least convincing, participants were divided on the issues of feminist leadership. One participant stated that "I can understand, accept and defend the feminist posture perfectly, but I have more difficulty framing leadership in this context. A leader must have certain qualities, namely in relation to the people he/she leads, and this does not depend (or should not depend) on whether he/she is a man or a woman." Another participant noted that they would like to see more commitment and participation from the leaders. Most participants agreed that they would be able to apply the contents of the webinar in their work. They expressed an interest in gaining more knowledge on a number of topics: leadership styles for different organization types; explore in more detail the way decisions are made; good examples of how these challenges described in today's webinar are met.

4. Outcomes from the Two-Day Leadership Programme

As part of the GEARING ROLES project, a 1.5 days training was organised on Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making. Originally intended to be held in-person at the GEARING-Roles conference in Istanbul, the training was transformed into an online format, and was delivered over five 90-minute sessions over 18th, 19th and 20th November 2020.

The training was designed for women mid-level and senior managers in research and innovation institutions. It was grounded in best practice in leadership and decision-making in research and innovation, drawing on the latest research and analysis in the field of structural change, as well as practical input from women leaders in higher education across Europe. It is envisaged that an in-person session will take place in June 2021, in combination with the pairing event that will take place at UDEUSTO.

The learning objectives were:

- Critically analyse the gender dimensions of leadership and decision-making
- Understand gender stereotypes related to leadership and decision-making and explore how these can be challenged
- Identify common biases and resistances women may experience in leadership – at the individual and institutional level - and find ways to address these
- Develop skills and networks for leadership for structural change

In line with best practice in gender training, the workshop was highly participatory, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the issues and topics covered. A range of tools and methods were used to maximise the potential of the online training format, in order to provide an experiential and dynamic learning experience for all participants. The training drew on emerging best practices in feminist methodologies for online training.

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In advance of the training, participants were asked to complete the following activities:

1. Write a brief introduction to be shared with the participants of the training (3-4 bullet points)
2. Find statistics for women in leadership and decision-making positions at your institution
3. Prepare 2-3 examples of challenges, gender bias or resistances you or your colleagues have faced in leadership and decision-making at your institution. For aspiring leaders, what bias or resistances do you anticipate, if any?
4. Prepare 1-2 questions to ask a senior female manager in research

On the registration form, participants were asked to answer the following questions:

- What leadership experience do you currently have?
- What is your ambition for your leadership career?
- What do you consider to be your strengths as a leader?
- What do you consider to be your weaknesses as a leader?
- How could this training help you in your leadership career?
- Please identify any special requirements that may affect your participation - e.g. childcare/caring responsibilities, language level, visual or hearing impairment, etc.

The data collected from the preparation and registration forms was used to develop a tailor-made training, taking into account the specific needs, interests and standpoints of the participants. Several participants indicated difficulties with childcare arrangements during the training, while others were concerned that they would not be able to follow closely due to their level of English. These issues were taken into account accordingly.

The programme was structured in five sessions, as follows:

DAY 1

Session 1, 9.30-11am: Data and Definitions

Session 2, 11.30am-1pm: Challenges, biases and resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making

DAY 2

Session 3, 9.30am-11am: Building skills and confidence to meet challenges

Session 4, 11.30am-1pm: Panel: women leaders in higher education

DAY 3

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Session 5, 9.30am-11am: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

In terms of participants, the following table contains the attendance details:

Position	Institution
Project Researcher	IGOT
Assistant Professor	IGOT
Editorial Team Leader in a Scientific Publication	IGOT
SU Gender Director	SABANCI
Marketing and Institutional Director	SABANCI
Human Resources Director	SABANCI
Vice Dean of Research	SABANCI
Chief Financial Officer	SABANCI
Researcher	OBU
Director of CDPRP	OBU
Programme Manager	ETAg
Executive Director	ETAg
Head of Department	ETAg
Head of Office	ETAg
HR Manager	UDEUSTO
Dean of the Law School	UDEUSTO
Vice-Rector of Research and Knowledge Transfer	UDEUSTO
Project Manager	UDEUSTO

4.1. Session 1: Data and Definitions

The session was opened by María López Belloso from UDEUSTO, who introduced the trainer Lucy Ferguson. To begin, the trainer launched a poll to ask how participants were feeling as an

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icebreaker activity. She then introduced the participants by institution, using the biographical data provided. Next, the session reviewed the expectations previously shared by the participants, and then presented the learning objectives and outline of the training.

This was followed by a quiz on key statistics on gender equality in leadership and decision-making using a mixture of EU level data and that provided on partner institutions by the participants. This demonstrated the diversity in gender issues between the project partners. The participants then shared an image of a “typical” university leader in the chat. They then moved into four breakout rooms to work on the group activity on leadership strengths and weaknesses, which was followed by a discussion in plenary.

Discussions and Key Issues

In breakout rooms, two groups of participants discussed their perceived strengths, as submitted via the registration forms. Examples included:

“Ability to hear suggestions from other colleagues; Put my suggestions for debate, not imposing them; Generate consensus.”

“Being supportive, setting an example”

“I adore people and I love to see how they improve as professionals in their careers”

“Discipline and humaneness”

“Collegiate, fair, approachable”

“Direct, ready to compromise, emphatic”

Some participants suggested these to be aspirations rather than existing characteristics, while others recognised these strengths in their own leadership styles. They were then asked to reflect on what their male colleagues might consider their strengths to be. These included: problem solving, decision making, result oriented, focused, practical and quickly deliver results, decision making, agile, good negotiator, strategic. It was suggested that while the characteristics may be similar, women tend to be more modest and not use superlatives, compared to their male colleagues.

The second two groups discussed the weaknesses previously submitted, such as:

“Softness, impatience, lack of assertiveness in certain situations (for example working with men older than me)”

“I feel fragile when I receive criticism and very hesitant in making decisions.”

“Reconciling the high workload pressures with being an authentic, supporting and caring leader”

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“I think I am too doubtful and insecure, sometimes I take too long, and I consider too many perspectives.”

“Sometimes too collaborative, trying to please too many people. This can lead to indecision.”

Need the approval of all (trying to please to many people);

Some suggested that male colleagues may be less open to acknowledge their weaknesses. Others believed that male colleagues seem to have more confidence, more courage, less empathy to take decisions, which could be considered a strength but also a weakness.

Overall, the activity allowed for a discussion around gender stereotypes in leadership, and to what extent these were out of date or still relevant.

4.2. Session 2: Challenges, Biases and Resistances to Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

At the beginning of the session, participants were provided with two articles discussing women’s leadership in the Covid-19 response. Following this, there was an open discussion around the key issues, such as: Do women have natural characteristics that make them better leaders? What is the role of “love” in leadership? Is this kind of argument helpful? The responses were varied, with a nuanced discussion of the issues and some suggestions about what qualities make a “21st century leader”, regardless of gender stereotypes.

Following this, the trainer presented a brief categorisation of leadership challenges into personal/individual and institutional challenges. Participants then broke into groups and shared leadership challenges they had experienced. Those challenges categorised by the participants as personal/individual challenges included the inequalities in the gendered division of labour at home, and how to balance work/life. Another issue was the fact that men often depreciate labour conducted by women. Participants identified with the difficulty in being recognised. There is a stereotype about women, relating them to feelings, and that creates an imaginary reality that links female leadership as hysterical or emotional. Other challenges were characterised as institutional, for example: the glass ceiling for women in upper administrative positions; not being part of male-bonding outside of office hours prevents us from being a part of decision-making processes and information sharing; discrimination in the context of implementing maternity leaves, etc. One group suggested that “none of these quotations are due to the personality of those women, they are caused by the institutional culture.” This was a valuable discussion to allow for distinction between “fixing women” vs “fixing institutions” to be discussed.

4.3. Session 3: Building Skills and Confidence to Meet Challenges

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This session was mostly taken up with leadership role plays. Participants were invited to suggest scenarios which they found particularly challenging. They chose to highlight the difficulty of saying no to extra work when it was presented as essential for the team. This scenario was recreated with two different participants, with the trainer playing the “unreasonable colleague”. Each time, a worst case scenario was played out. After that the other participants were asked to suggest alternative ways to deal with the situation. The role plays were then repeated employing the new techniques.

After the role play activity, the trainer launched a poll asking whether participants felt more confident in dealing with leadership challenges than before the training. Out of 18 participants, 14 said yes, 4 said the same as before, and 2 answered not sure/don't know.

4.4. Session 4: Panel: Women Leaders in Higher Education

In order to make the most of the online format, a panel session was organized with three invited female senior managers in universities. Each speaker was invited to present for 5-7 minutes, reflecting on some key questions, for example:

- As a female senior manager, do you experience particular challenges that you think a male senior manager does not face?
- Would you call yourself a feminist female leader? Why/why not?
- To what extent is it possible to reconcile feminist leadership with senior management roles in higher education?

The speakers were Christine Musselin, CNRS Research Professor, Centre de Sociologie des Organisations, Sciences Po - CNRS; Fiona Mackay FAcSS, FRSE, Professor of Politics, School of Social and Political Science, University of Edinburgh; and Gemma Irvine, Vice-President for Equality & Diversity, Maynooth University.

Musselin's presentation explored her trajectory as a leader, explaining that she had experienced few examples of gender discrimination in her career, and that her main support and encouragement had come from men during throughout the process. However, she highlighted that often women wait until they have the perfect CV before applying for promotion, whereas men are more likely to apply even without being fully qualified. She highlighted some of the tools she had used in promoting gender issues as an academic leader, as well as pointing to some remaining challenges. These included the importance of remembering that gender inequality is not the only issue, and focussing also on social, racial and other forms of discriminations.

In contrast, Fiona Mackay's presentation focussed on the challenges of being an explicitly feminist leader in higher education. She outlined her trajectory as an “accidental” academic, to “reluctant” leader, to proactive manager. Mackay then discussed some of the challenges of the Head of School role, such as the gendered labour expected of female leaders, and the lack of

cultural modes of authority on which women have to draw, except that of “mother”. Nevertheless, she reaffirmed the value of care in leadership and suggested that positional power can help to redefine leadership (feminism “by stealth”). Finally, she reflected that for her, academic management had been personally empowering, and she found the “insider” role an important strategy for change.

Gemma Irvine’s presentation involved a visual tool to highlight the trajectory of her career, comparing academic and non-academic routes to senior management. This visual explanation allowed for an in-depth analysis of both personal and structural factors, and how these had influenced Gemma’s journey to senior management.

Following this, Irvine discussed unconscious bias, as well as using an iceberg analogy to describe “overtly” assault, harassment and discrimination vs “all the little moments that make someone feel they don’t belong”. She then highlighted some of the barriers and enablers to gender equality in leadership and decision-making in higher education.

Following the presentations, a number of questions were asked by the participants. These included:

Q: How were you able to manage/achieve work/life balance?

Q: How do you deal with resilience, career-management, and self-care?

When answering these questions, Fiona Mackay stated that:

“It is important to keep interests (reading fiction, going to the theatre, seeing friends). In terms of work-life balance, I’ve found the analogy of juggling balls helpful - you’re going to drop one or two, so the important thing is to work out which ones will bounce, which ones are glass and will break if you drop the; and which ones are lead and will smash your toes! I’ve also found it helpful to think about academic careers over the long haul - there will be periods of stasis and that’s ok. I think we need to challenge ‘heroic’ ideas of leadership - of being endlessly available. And, as Gemma said, messages on emails about your availability etc are really useful ways of chipping away”. Fiona Mackay

On its side, Gemma Irvine replied that:

“When I was a Dean, I worked every Saturday afternoon on my own research and even wrote a book during my term. I also kept one class because I was afraid of the “time after” and wanted not to completely forget my previous job, as being an academic leader and an academic are very different jobs. But I had very little time for me. I therefore took dance class after I stepped down and played 2 hours guitar a day, in the evening instead of answering emails. As for the work/life balance, it was nevertheless

not too difficult as my two children were already adults and my partner was helpful and supportive.” Gemma Irvine

Q: How do you manage upwards? How do you manage more senior people than you?

Answers included several strategies, such as: be solution focused (along with the problem); frame everything around their agenda; create actionable demands (ensure that what you ask for, can be actioned); make sure that you also foster collaboration in your approach; prepare evidence, pointing to data and supporting evidence; showing the added value of the suggestion, it is in their best interests; asking for their insight and input into my work, to get them into the conversation; code-switching between norms and cultures in the different groups (e.g. talk in a similar tone with group members).

Q: What would you advise, how to behave if you are treated as an empty place just because of being female, especially by elderly men in higher positions? Do you have any good tricks on how to become visible if you do not have a strong voice and if you do not want to become aggressive, but would prefer to stay calm?

Q: Usually, at least in my country, it is understood that senior management must have almost total availability, regardless of time or day of the week. It's hard to say that you don't read your email permanently or that you don't do some work at those times. This means that many people, and especially women, prefer to say no to offers rather than to access top leadership positions. Excluding these moments of pandemic where this may be more "understandable", how can this situation be reversed?

Christine Musselin dealt with this questions by stating that:

“This is a good reason for accepting a senior management position as a woman because you can then try to change this when you are in such a position: not organize meetings very late or very early in the morning, not send emails over the weekend or in the night. In my experience, men reacted well to these kinds of arguments. They also feel obliged to be always available but rarely dare say it.”Christine Musselin

Q: What is each of them's key learning from their leadership experience that they find important to share?

Again, Christine Musselin provided the key message about the need to differentiate being an academic and being in a management position in academia:

“It confirmed something I already felt in my own research on universities: management positions in universities are more and more professionalized. You rely (and it is very important and necessary) on your experience as an academic but it is a completely

different job that I learnt. It took me one year after I stopped to learn and appreciate my previous job again.”

The panel session generated a lot of discussion and was a very useful exercise for both participants and presenters. It was agreed that further sessions of this nature would be helpful for developing women leaders in research institutions.

4.5. Session 5: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

The final session was dedicated to developing Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making. Participants worked in groups with colleagues from their own institutions. At the end of the activity, each team had a rough draft of an action plan - at the individual and the institutional level. These will be developed further in the in-person training at UDEUSTO in June 2021.

Actions at the individual level included:

Ambitions

- To be able to enjoy any activity that I need to perform and at the same time be able to self-acknowledge my own potential.
- Have the capacity, by being empathic and assertive, to manage the challenges and conflicts of my team.
- My goal in improving my leadership is to be more inspirational to my team. I want to have the ability to enthuse my team to see the future with optimism and achieve new goals. To join them about the possibility of a different and more challenging future, optimizing efforts, development and performance.
- I like my current position, would like to continue for some years and improve my leadership skills. Then perhaps try to apply for a position abroad.
- My ambition as a leader – to be better at my current position and further develop my strengths as a leader. To learn more tricks to use in different situations. Perhaps apply for a position connected to the environmental topic in the future.
- I do not necessarily want to work in a higher position, but I would rather want to be better in my current position.
- To be an authentic and caring leader reconciling the time pressures and workload of academia with my desire to provide care and support to colleagues. To say no.
- To get experience outside academia, e.g. more portfolio career through a non-executive board position, using my academic expertise in another context.

Skills needed to achieve this (personal/individual level)

- Assertiveness, self-esteem.

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- Strength, courage, confidence, empathy and assertiveness
- Enthusiasm, vision
- I have only been a leader for 1 year, and would need to gain experience. Improve my time management skills.
- Assertiveness, being more motivating and better skills for team building in heterogeneous teams. Delegating tasks and time management.
- Prioritising and allocating time for caring and continuous reflective thinking. Assertiveness and strategic thinking on decisions
- More languages, strategic planning skills, time management, more experiences and tricks to deal with different situations
- More technical aspects, e.g. financial management, operations etc

Support I need to achieve this (institutional level)

- Stability
- The complicity of the manager of the complementary area
- I think the question is more of putting the institutional interest before personal interest in what concerns individual career progression
- This training was very helpful to see another perspective of leadership, and to listen to inspiring talks. Coaching.
- Trainings, cooperation with other leaders to see how they work, discussions in different likeminded groups (like here today)
- I would need a coaching training, similar to those that were discussed yesterday.
- Trainings, cooperation with other leaders to see how they work, discussions in different likeminded groups (like here today)
- Institutional support to allow time for reflection. Mentor to help with strategic decision making
- Coaching/training in executive education/leadership

Steps to take to reach this goal

- Internal networking, getting external funds, be attached to my goals instead of answering to other people's requests
- Recognise the huge work done, redefine our mission and our projects, sharing with the team the steps in this vision. Making it shared.
- Team building and workshops at institutional level. Personally, not trying to do everything at the same time and have the courage to say no sometimes.
- Apply for leadership training/ coaching. Also, individual reading is not a bad idea. Networking with other leaders is very inspiring.
- Protect some time in my calendar for reflection. Identify a mentor
- Plan time for training. Study languages. Avoid burning-out.

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- Look for and participate in different leadership training, be part of different networks where are likeminded people. TEDX talks. Look for successful role models.
- Read resources on non-executive directors responsibilities and tasks. Attend training and network.

Next, in groups, participants discussed some key points regarding developing an Institutional Action Plan per consortium member. They discussed: ambitions for gender equality in leadership and decision-making in the future of the institution; what skills do women leaders and potential women leaders need to achieve this (personal/individual level); what support women leaders and potential women leaders (institutional level); and what steps can be taken to reach this goal.

5. Conclusion

With regard to the workshops that have been delivered in the context of the pairing events of the project we believe the general objectives of the training session have been met.

In both pairing events, top management bodies of the institutions were actively involved (Deans, Vice-Rectors and HR Managers, among others). Their presence, participation, and critical reflection in this action directly contributes to raising awareness of the causes and consequences of women's limited participation in management positions, and about their role in the process of change, which is in itself a major achievement of these workshops.

The webinar series offered participants an opportunity to explore key issues related to gender equality in leadership and decision-making in higher education, opening questions and ideas for mutual learning and constructive debate. The open webinars allowed the GEARING ROLES project to reach a wide audience, and covered the key issues of bias, resistances, and feminine values in leadership. The closed webinars were also very useful for engaging senior leaders in participant institutions, including male leaders. These allowed for an in-depth exploration of some of the different perspectives around gender equality and leadership across different institutions. Overall, the evaluations were positive and participants were satisfied with the online format. However, it was noted that having the opportunity to meet in person would make it even better, and this should be considered for university leaders at GEARING-Roles institutions as soon as face to face training resumes.

Finally, overall, the Leadership Programme was a stimulating and participatory experience, very well valued by participants (Annex 11). Some key substantive points were discussed, regarding the future of leadership, the role of "academic care work", and the challenges of feminist leadership. It will be important to follow up periodically with participants to ensure the momentum of this workshop is not lost. Suggestions raised on how to do this include: further online sessions on specific topics; coaching and mentoring; and the importance of networking

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among senior female leaders. The in-person workshop at UDEUSTO will be used to review the action plans and reflect on the key questions discussed in the training.

Taken together, we believe that these awareness-raising activities on leadership and decision making have been extremely important in the context of the GEARING ROLES project, to better respond to its mainstream goal of promoting more successful implementations of gender equality plans. Consistent with previous research in this field (Gartzia, 2021), we found that gender equality in business action has to be closely aligned with the organizational strategy and needs to involve decision-makers to be sustainable in the practice. Managerial implication and support were critical for the successful implementation of gender equality plans in our institutions, as they allowed managers to have a critical role in institutional change, which is a necessary step in the process. Gender equality plans need to be publicly supported and made visible by decision making bodies and to do that it is critical to ensure a critical understanding of gender-related issues by key agents in the organization, ensuring a more realistic implementation of the measures and activities listed in gender equality plans. For instance, managers can frame gender equality plans as an organizational priority that is openly supported by them, giving explicit importance to the topic.

The change management and gender literature has also captured these complexities and suggested specific ways in which decision-making bodies can get involved in gender action. If efforts to integrate gender equality in organizational goals are not alignment with the organizational strategy and structure, they are likely to fail (Gartzia, 2021). From a change management perspective, incorporating such utilitarian approach is important because it allows a more realistic implementation of change efforts (Scott & Jaffe, 1998; Hirschhorn, 2002; Knodel, 2004; Kotter, 2008). Convincing decision makers and change agents in the first place is important because they have the necessary resources to promote deeper transformations in the organizational structure and dynamics. Consistent with this idea, these apparently minor, incremental transformations of gender awareness of managers and decision makers are critical for implementation of gender equality plans, as they have the potential to accumulate and ultimately allow changing organizational structures with more substantial transformations that can transform gender roles in the broader organizational strategy.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Presentation used in OBU Pairing Event workshop

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Presentation Title: XXXXX

Presentation Date: XXXX

Presentation Location: XXXX

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender in organizations: basic areas
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: identifying resistances and challenges

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender in organizations: basic areas
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: identifying resistances and challenges

1. Encourage **equal representation and participation** of women in leadership and decision-making
2. Analyse and **redefine leadership models** from a gender perspective.
3. Support **awareness raising** and behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership

3) Support **awareness raising** and behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership

- **Who?** Decision making boards + other management positions
- **What?:** "Raise awareness of **causes and consequences of women's limited representation** in leadership and the potential value of stereotypically feminine dimensions"
- **Outcomes:** Compiled in report (**Deliv. 5.5; Month 12**)

3) Support **awareness raising** and behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership

- **Who?** Decision making boards + other management positions
- **What?:** "Raise awareness of **causes and consequences of women's limited representation** in leadership and the potential value of stereotypically feminine dimensions"
- **Outcomes:** Compiled in report (**Deliv. 5.5; Month 12**)

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
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Gender Quotas:

Problem

At least 40% by 2020 (EC, 2012)

25.3% women in listed
companies in EU member states

2018 Report on equality between women and men in the EU

Figure 13: Representation of women and men on the boards of the largest listed companies in the EU, October 2017

Source: European Institute for Gender Equality, Gender Statistics Database

WHY SO FEW WOMEN?

Leadership Stereotypes

- self-confident
- assertive
- takes charge
- solves problems
- inspire others
- takes risks
- action oriented

Think Manager-Think Male

- Schein (1973): “think manager-think male stereotype”
 - Participants rated successful middle managers, men, or women (rated one group)
 - On 92 traits that differentiate between men and women
 - Compare men-leaders similarity to women-leaders similarity on mean-level ratings
- Koenig et al. (2011) located 50 studies of this type

Consequences: Prejudice Against Women As Leaders

Gender Stereotypes

Men are dominant, assertive, self-confident, & take charge.

Women are nice, friendly, socially skilled, sensitive

Leader Role Stereotype

Leaders are self-confident, assertive, take charge, solve problems, inspire others

One of the most important reasons why there are only a few women in top management positions

Domestic Division of Labor

(European Commission, 2019)

Domestic Work

Childcare (Leave)

Contemporary Arguments Against Gender-Neutral Language

Hellen Vergoossen¹, Emma A Bäck², Anna Lindqvist³ & Marie Gustafsson Sendén¹
¹Stockholm University, ²Gothenburg University, ³Lund University

Stockholm University

LUND UNIVERSITY

UNIVERSITY OF GOTHENBURG

Introduction

In 2015, a gender-neutral pronoun ('hen') was introduced in Swedish as a complement to 'hon' (she) and 'han' (he). Adding a gender-neutral pronoun differs from previous gender-fair language reforms in that it does not aim to make language more fair for both reforms, but rather to make language reforms have an impact on non-sexist communication. Previous research (Sendén et al., 2015) against a previous structured them into four categories: 'Change is too difficult', 'There are other words to use', 'Freedom of speech', and 'Attention thief'. This research also is also relevant to the introduction of 'hen' instead of 'han' or 'hon'.

udes towards 'hen' word. 38.1% of toward 'hen'. Their rized according to erton, 1998).

gories, 19% were its belonged to old

categories to old a subcategory of r as an exclusively nders – accept it!”)

‘There are other words to use’ is a subcategory of ‘Change is too difficult’.

Two categories were completely new: **‘Attention Thief’** contains arguments concerning ‘hen’ distracting attention from the message. **‘Gender Identity is Important’** includes arguments on the importance of gender information in communication, and the notion that lack of such information means depersonalization of others and barrier in communication.

Figure 1: Arguments against gender-neutral language. Grey circles has been found in previous research about language reforms, Yellow categories include new arguments, against non-binary languages reforms. Overlap indicates relatedness between categories

Conclusions

The main categories in previous research remained common, such as **‘Change is too Difficult’** which together with its new subcategory **‘There are Other Words to Use’** accounts for 35% of all arguments. **‘Hostility and Ridicule toward the Proponents of Change’** (12%), includes arguments that diminish the word itself and its proponents (e.g., ‘hen is ridiculous because it means ‘hen’ in English’). **‘Freedom of Speech’** (10%), comprises arguments such as ‘it feels like an unpleasant and authoritarian imposition from above’. Eight old categories hardly occurred at all in this sample (9% in total).

Arguments against gender-neutral language partially tap into the same categories of arguments found against previous forms of feminist language reforms, but also belong to some new categories. Novel is the focus on challenging the idea of gender as being nonbinary. While ideas such as sexism being acceptable or sexist language not being sexist were very uncommon in our sample, the idea that gender identities (and either male or female) are important and that language should reflect this was common.

This research was funded by The Swedish Research Council

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 Sendén, M., Bäck, E. A., & Lindqvist, A. (2015). *Attitudes towards gender-neutral language: A study of Swedish academics and their attitudes and behavior*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6, 1-10.
 Vergoossen, H., Bäck, E. A., Lindqvist, A., & Sendén, M. (2021). *Contemporary Arguments Against Gender-Neutral Language: A Thematic Analysis of Swedish Academic Texts*. *Journal of Language and Communication Disorders*, 3, 1-14.

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OTHER ISSUES & EFFECTS (GEP)

Women in the EU, across the economy, earn on average over ...

16 % less per hour
than men

(European Commission 2018)

Figure 5: EU-28 trends in gender pay gap in unadjusted form, 2010-2016

Source: Eurostat

In STEM Fields, Many Employers Hire “John” over “Jennifer”

Blind auditions and Gender Bias

<https://www.theguardian.com/women-in-leadership/2013/oct/14/blind-auditions-orchestras-gender-bias>

ORGANIZATION/BRAND IMAGE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

FORTUNE | MFW

Chris Rattcliffe-Bloomberg via Getty Images

TWITTER

Exclusive: Twitter to Give All New Parents 20 Weeks of Paid Leave

Michal Lev-Ram
Apr 05, 2016

May 1 will be a happy day for Twitter employees—at least those expecting a baby. The social media

<https://asl.doubleclick.net/ddm/clk/318137558;146603681,m>

FORTUNE | Tech

TELEVISION

This Is How Much it Costs Women to Be Contestants on 'The...'

INTERNATIONAL TRADE
Why America Is Taking A Back Seat To Chile In Trade Talks

HOUSING PI
3 Ways the Housing Market Rec...

Facebook's office. Photograph by Justin Holmstrom - Getty Images

FACEBOOK

A subtle change gave Facebook's icons more gender equality

Kia Kokalchess
Jul 07, 2015

An image may be worth a thousand words, but a Facebook icon represents literally millions of people.

The magnitude of the symbolism of Facebook's

Google Diversity

HOME HIRING INCLUSION EDUCATION COMMUNITIES

"A diverse mix of voices leads to better discussions, decisions, and outcomes for everyone."

-Sundar Pichai, CEO, Google

LEARN MORE

Using technology to identify gender bias

Enter machine learning: an emerging technology that makes it possible to understand huge amounts of complex data.

With support from [Google.org's Global Impact Challenge](#), the Geena Davis Institute on Gender in Media teamed up with Google machine learning engineer Hartwig Adam and USC's Viterbi School of Engineering's Dr. Shri Narayanan, the Niki & C. L. Max Nikias Chair in Engineering, and his SAIL Laboratory, to develop software that accurately measures how often we see and hear women on-screen. "Media arts are an amazing source of information that can provide insights into who we are as society," says Dr. Narayanan.

"We need to engage with people in different fields... and work together on addressing specific problems using machine intelligence."

Hartwig Adam
Machine Learning Engineer at Google

Listen

"If a gap exists, we'll address it. And we'll continue our work to make sure we maintain pay equity," Apple wrote in the report. "We've achieved pay equity in the United States for similar roles and performance. Women earn one dollar for every dollar male employees earn. And underrepresented minorities earn one dollar for every dollar white employees earn."

Inclusion & Diversity

Diversity and Innovation Creating Opportunities

We want Apple to be a reflection of the world around us.

These numbers show our progress and represent our ongoing commitment to greater inclusion and diversity.

Our hiring trend over the past three years.

We're steadily attracting more and more underrepresented talent.

New hires are employees hired during the 12-month period ending in June of each year.

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender in organizations: basic areas
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: identifying resistances and challenges

- Managers= Agents of Change
- “Actors in charge of the **day-to-day management** of the organisation”
- (In the context of research organisations → faculty deans, heads of departments or directors of services,...)

Culture

- Informal behaviours
- Beliefs/attitudes/values
- Social/group norms

Strategy

- Formal logic of org. objectives
- Strategic plans / objectives
- Decision-making

Different evolution/change mechanisms

Mixture of management decisions and **staff knowledge/experiences**

Determined by management decisions and **need for adaptation to external changes**

Work & Stress
Vol. 24, No. 2, April–June 2010, 107–139

 Routledge
Taylor & Francis Group

Are leaders' well-being, behaviours and style associated with the affective well-being of their employees? A systematic review of three decades of research

Janne Skakon^{a*}, Karina Nielsen^b, Vilhelm Borg^b and Jaime Guzman^c

^aInstitute of Psychology, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark; ^bNational Research Centre for the Working Environment, Copenhagen, Denmark; ^cOccupational Health & Safety Agency for Healthcare in British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada

- Leadership style and followers' health
- Leaders' lifestyle (long hours, travel, pressure, WFC,...)
- Leaders' health and effectiveness (outcomes and followers' responses)
- Physical health vs. Psychological Health

So, what's the role of leaders/managers in GEPs?

2. TEAMWORK: WHAT CAN WE DO?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

- What is the role of managers in a GEP?
 - 1. Publicly support the GEP;
 - 2. Ensure the practical implementation of the measures, procedures and activities listed in the GEP
 - 3. Promote incentives to ensure the integration of a gender dimension in research and teaching
 - 4. Instruct the relevant units to provide information and data to monitor the implementation of the GEP and progress towards gender equality.

- **Valuing managers' contribution as agents of change**
- 'Our institution has committed to high standards with respect to gender equality and our rector made a nice speech about this last week. And yet, without your knowledge of the organisation and of the people who work in it, we have no chance of success. As managers you are best placed to help us in detecting room for improvement, and to co-create and test effective solutions with us.'
- **Internal stimulation** 'Since our communication department adopted a gender-sensitive communication, our institution has been quoted as an example at the national level,[...] news about gender equality issues which are now more frequently displayed on the website are the most tweeted and shared on Facebook. It would be great to trigger the same dynamics in our departments and faculties and to engage in discussion with students.'
- **Referring to specific cases of management** 'The case of harassment we had to deal with last year has been extremely costly for us. The case was largely commented on both within and outside the institution, we appeared to be insensitive and not proactive and eventually our liability was mentioned in legal proceedings. We knew this could happen. Let's start dealing with this seriously.'

- **Access to funding and competitiveness** ’
- Attention to the gender dimension is extensively referred to in Horizon 2020 and this reflects in the current work programme. If we take this on board in our proposal it could increase our competitiveness and our chances of being funded.’
- **Internal synergies**
- ‘Our department of sociology has a rich record of supporting work-life balance among its academic staff. Did you know that a **small fund was created to support childcare for those with parental responsibilities who wish to actively participate in international projects and conferences?** Let’s plan a meeting with their management and a few researchers to learn from their experience!’

- Summary of GEAR Tool
- Setting up a GEP which is **fully and publicly supported** by senior managers and leaders will help in giving visibility to gender equality.
- This is to **ensure a collective, shared understanding** of the importance of gender equality and related work. Frame it as an **organisational priority**.

Culture: 4 Attributes

Shared

Groupal phenomenon (norms, expectatives, unwritten group values)

Pervasive

Present everywhere (physical environment, rituals, visible symbols, legends, stories, beliefs, mental models about how to respond to context)

Enduring

Guides behaviour in the long term; Resistant to change, Self-Reinforcing pattern (Attraction-Selection-Attrition Model; *Schneider, 1987*)

Implicit

Subliminal, but sends very clear and effective messages (silent language)

“Culture eats strategy for breakfast”

Successful leaders/organisations will use culture as a fundamental management tool

Culture: Lines for action

1

Leaders have to **become aware** of the culture operating at their organisation.

2

They should define a **target culture**, to which they aspire.

3

Develop/Master organisational **change practices**.

Necessary to approach organisational objectives (and equality) through a culture change, using **simple models and methods** for goal identification and setting.

Strategies for Overcoming Resistance to Change

- Education and Communication
 - Show the logic behind the change

- Participation
 - Participation in the decision process lessens resistance

- Building Support and Commitment
 - Counseling, therapy, or new-skills training

- Promote critical and creative thinking
 - Create an organizational context in which creative and critical thinking is welcome and valued

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2. TEAMWORK: WHAT CAN WE DO?

- 1) Identify strengths and resistances:
 - Gender in management (Sex + Gender)
 - Rewards/Promotion
 - Work Life Balance
 - Org. Brand / Communication
 - Cultural Values
 - Leaders' Awareness

- 2) What can we do from our leadership and decision making positions to promote gender equality?

Take-home messages?

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions
to transform Gender Roles

Thank you

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YELLOW WINDOW

Annex 2: Template used in OBU Pairing Event workshop

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Annex 3: Presentation used in IGOT Pairing Event workshop

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Presentation Title: Development of decision-making processes

Presentation Date: 26-11-2019

Presentation Location: IGOT - Lisbon

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Structure

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender & Decision-making in organizations
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: flows of decision-making

1. Encourage **equal representation and participation** of women in leadership and decision-making
2. Analyse and **redefine leadership models** from a gender perspective.
3. Support **awareness raising** and behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership

1) Encourage **equal representation and participation** of women in leadership and decision-making

- **Who?** Decision making boards + other management positions
- **What?:** "Raise awareness of **causes and consequences of women's limited representation** in leadership and the potential value of stereotypically feminine dimensions"
- **Outcomes:** Decision making flow charts (**Deliv. 5.2**)

1) Encourage **equal representation and participation** of women in leadership and decision-making

- **Who?** Decision making boards + other management positions

- **What?:** "Raise awareness of **causes and consequences of women's limited representation** in leadership and the potential value of stereotypically feminine dimensions"

- **Outcomes:** Decision making flow charts (Deliv. 5.2)

Structure

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender & Decision-making in organizations
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: flows of decision-making

25% women in listed
companies in EU member states

WHY SO FEW WOMEN?

LEADERSHIP STEREOTYPES

- self-confident
- assertive
- takes charge
- solves problems
- inspire others
- takes risks
- action oriented

LEADERSHIP STEREOTYPES

Consequences: Prejudice Against Women As Leaders

Gender Stereotypes

Men are dominant, assertive, self-confident, & take charge.

Women are nice, friendly, socially skilled, sensitive

Leader Role Stereotype

Leaders are self-confident, assertive, take charge, solve problems, inspire others

Incongruity

Men and Leaders match

Women and Leaders don't match as well

One of the most important reasons why there are only a few women in top management positions

DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g978T58gELo&feature=youtu.be>

- Quality + Effectiveness in Decision-Making: Source of Competitiveness for HEIs
- Should be inspired by the principle of transparency
- Decision taken based on appropriate information

Two ways of looking at decision - making processes at HEIs:

- Anarchic, spontaneous organizations where decision - making is largely conducted in an unstructured and informal way (Cohen et al. 1972).

- Orderly and structured processes (Shattock 2003).

DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES

Professionalization and managerialism

More structured decision-making processes (Rixom 2011)

However, the informal side in decision-making processes plays an important role.

DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES

- Diversity in participation in decision-making processes -> higher quality solutions.
- Exclusion of women in the academic field:
 - Decreasing the overall quality of decision-making outcome at the institutional level,
 - Direct harmful effects in terms of research opportunities, scientific productivity,
 - And, ultimately, promotion and career advancement of female researchers.

Gendered patterns of inclusion

DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES: BIASES

In STEM Fields, Many Employers Hire “John” over “Jennifer”

Gender Bias in the process itself

VS.

Gender Bias in the criteria

Structure

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender & Decision-making in organizations
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: flows of decision-making

- Managers= Agents of Change
- “Actors in charge of the **day-to-day management** of the organisation”
- (In the context of higher education & research organizations → **faculty deans, heads of departments or directors of services,...**)

WHY YOU? LEADERS AND DECISION MAKING

Culture

- Informal behaviours
- Beliefs/attitudes/values
- Social/group norms

Strategy

- Formal logic of org. objectives
- Strategic plans / objectives
- **Decision-making**

Different evolution/change mechanisms

Mixture of management decisions and **staff knowledge/experiences**

Determined by management decisions and **need for adaptation to external changes**

WHY LEADERS?

- What is the role of managers in a GEP?
- 1. **Publicly support** the GEP;
- 2. Ensure the **practical implementation of the measures, procedures and activities** listed in the GEP
- 3. **Promote incentives** to ensure the integration of a gender dimension in research and teaching
- 4. **Instruct the relevant units to provide information and data to monitor** the implementation of the GEP and progress towards gender equality.

WHY LEADERS?

- In particular:
- Shape bias-free (or reduced-bias) decision-making processes.
- Reduce informalities
- **Fully and publicly support** the balance in decision-making bodies will give visibility to gender equality in power positions.

WHY LEADERS?

“Lay down stepping stones towards change”

- Recognise issues arising from the existence of bias as a point where we should keep an eye.
- Set example for other leaders (deans, heads of department, academic group leaders)

Structure

1. Introduction: WP5 Leadership
2. Gender & Decision-making in organizations
3. Why you?: Leaders and Decision-Making
4. Teamwork: flows of decision-making

TEAMWORK: WHAT CAN WE DO?

- 1) Which is the typical decision-making process to appoint a Dean at your University?
- 2) Identify gender biases in the process and/or the criteria.
- 3) How can the process be improved?

Decision-Making Flow

Take-home messages?

Annex 4: Template used in IGOT Pairing Event workshop

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Decision-Making Flow

Annex 5: Presentation used in Online Pairing Event workshop

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Título: Results from WP5 Questionnaire

Fecha: 29/03/2021

Localización: Universidad de Deusto (Bilbao) & online

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Our goals regarding Leadership:

Encourage equal representation and participation in leadership and decision-making.

Women

Analyse and redefine leadership models from a gender perspective

Communion

Support awareness raising and behavioural changes

Awareness / Change

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

Critical in current OB models

*Female Advantage**

Agentic Traits SELF	Competitive Daring Adventurous Aggressive Dominant Courageous	
Communal Traits OTHERS	Loving Understanding Kind Sensitive Sympathetic Affectionate	

Abele & Wojciszke, 2007; Gartzia & Baniandrés, 2019

*See Eagly, A. H., Gartzia, L., & Carli, L. L. (2014). Female Advantage: Revisited. In S. Kumra, R. Simpson, & R. J. Burke (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Gender in Organizations* Oxford University Press.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

Values

Communal values

"Helping Others", "Caring for Others", and "Attending to Others"

Achievement values

"Being accomplished", "Being competent", and "Being successful"

Power values

"Having power", "Demonstrating superiority", and "Having status"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

Leadership Styles

People Orientation vs. Task Orientation
(Quinn, 1997)

Mentor	Listen to the personal problems of group members Treat each individual in a sensitive, caring way Show concern for the needs of group members Show empathy and concern in dealing with group members
Task-Oriented	Focus on results for the group Ensure the group delivers on stated goals Push the group to meet objectives Emphasize the group's achievement of stated purposes

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Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

“Discrimination is no longer a problem”

“Gender equality is already achieved”

“Positive action is not needed”

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

WFC

The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life
The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil family responsibilities

FAMILY-SUPPORTIVE CULTURE

1. Work should be the primary priority in a person's life*
2. Long hours inside the office are the way to achieve advancement*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

N = 445 (65% women, 32% men)

Age range = 41-50 years

Tenure= 8.19 years (SD=7.61)

>50% at least one dependent children

61% Teaching/Research & 39% Administrative

53,6% Employees

35,3% Middle Managers

11,3% Top managers

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Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
2. Gender concerns
3. Work-Life Balance

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Communion: Individual traits

Communion > Agency

But lower for men...

And top managers...

'Think manager-think male'

(Koenig et al., 2011; Gartzia & van Knippenberg, 2016).

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Communion: Leadership styles (My supervisor)

Similar task/ rewards / stimulation (n.s.)

My supervisor's styles...

- 1. People Or. (62.3%; for women)
- 1. Task Or. (58,7%; for men)
- 2. Contingent rewards (58,6%)
- 4. Intellectual Stimulation (37%)

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Communion: Leadership Values

My supervisor values...

- 1. Achievement
"Being accomplished", "Being competent", and "Being successful"
- 2. Communion (women +)
"Helping Others", "Caring for Others", and "Attending to Others"
- 3. Power
"Having power", "Demonstrating superiority", and "Having status"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Evaluation: Identify our strengths and weaknesses

Survey to leaders and team members

- 1. Communion
 - 1.1. Individual traits
 - 1.2. Leadership Styles / Values
- 2. Gender concerns
- 3. Work-Life Balance

“Discrimination is no longer a problem”
 “Gender equality is already achieved”
 “Positive action is not needed”

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

2. Gender equality concerns

High awareness of discrimination

Discrimination against women is no longer a problem in my country*
 Society has reached the point where women and men have equal opportunities for achievement*

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3. Work-Life Balance Concerns

Similar WFC...

...but more with male leaders

WFC

The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life
 The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil family responsibilities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

4. Work-Life Balance Concerns

More WFC on the top...

WFC

The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life
 The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil family responsibilities

...women less received support

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

3. Work-Life Balance Concerns

FAMILY-SUPPORTIVE CULTURE

1. Work should be the primary priority in a person's life*
2. Long hours inside the office are the way to achieve advancement*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

What did we learn from this analysis?

LESSONS
LEARNED

Communion: "Female advantage"?

Still high resistance: meritocracy vs. gender equality + personal status quo

Cultural background and inertia (TM-TM)

Redefinition of workload/role of leaders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

@GearingRoles
@gearingroles
<http://gearingroles.eu>

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Annex 6: Template used in Online Pairing Event workshop 1

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LOTUS BLOSSOM

Annex 7: Presentation used in the first open webinar

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Webinar: “Bias and resistances: exploring
challenges to gender equality in leadership and
decision-making”

Presentation Date: 30th April 2020

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 programme,
under grant agreement no. 824536

- **Maria Silvestre, GEARING Roles**
- **Vasia Madesi, Gender Equality Academy**
- **Lucy Ferguson, Yellow Window**

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

6 GEPs

GEP COUNTRIES - UK, Portugal, Spain, Slovenia, Turkey, Estonia

STEPS OF THE PROCESS

Project

In line with the call goals GEARING-Roles ('Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to traNsform Gender ROLES') targets the questioning and transformation of traditional gender roles at the micro, meso, and macro levels, with four main Objectives:

Female Career Progression

To remove barriers to female recruitment and devise Personal Career Development Plans (PCDPs)

Education and research

To provide alternative references in traditionally male dominated areas (STEM) and in those where women are majority but kept under glass ceilings (Health & Care, Hum, Law, SSCC in general) by strengthening the gender dimension in research programs and methodologies, fostering gender-knowledge and scientific production in relation to gender and feminist studies, and by reinforcing women researchers' careers

Leadership and Decision-making

To address gender imbalances in the representation, processes, and the promotion of women leadership in research institutions

Promotion of Gender Equality in Research Organisations and Key Stakeholders for the Reinforcement of ERA

Disseminate the common framework and outputs for institutional gender assessment, planning, monitoring and evaluation to establish commitment to gender equality in major European stakeholder organisations and build a sustainable long-term network of organisations advancing gender equality

- ✓ Understand the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making
- ✓ Explore resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making
- ✓ Discuss strategies for tackling bias and resistances

Maxime Forest, Yellow Window

“Why Gender Equality should matter to Meritocracy and Academic Excellence: tackling gender bias in decision-making and leadership”

Lucy Ferguson, Yellow Window

How do we address resistances to achieving gender equality in leadership and decision-making?

“We should celebrate as a success cases where the status quo has to start to work hard to reproduce itself and has to invest resources and energy in resisting gender change. The need for visible resistance to positive change is a success. It is evidence of the chipping away of patriarchy; it might be chipping away really slowly, but it is changing.”

(Fiona Mackay, quoted in Aruna Rao, Joanne Sandler, David Kelleher, Carol Miller, *Gender at Work: Theory and Practice for 21st Century Organizations*, Routledge 2016)

“We should celebrate as a success cases where the status quo has to start to work hard to reproduce itself and has to invest resources and energy in resisting gender change. The need for visible resistance to positive change is a success. It is evidence of the chipping away of patriarchy; it might be chipping away really slowly, but it is changing.”

(Fiona Mackay, quoted in Aruna Rao, Joanne Sandler, David Kelleher, Carol Miller, *Gender at Work: Theory and Practice for 21st Century Organizations*, Routledge 2016)

Do you agree with this quotation?

- Collectively developing examples, definitions and categorisation
- Draws on a number of sources - [FESTA Handbook on Resistance to Gender Equality in Academia](#); [Lombardo and Mergaert 2013](#)
- Workshops on resistances to structural change in various Horizon 2020 projects
- Developing Toolkit for Dealing with Resistances

- **Why?** Specific resistance to gender equality or other issues
- **How?** Active/explicit, passive/implicit
- **Who?** Individual, group, institutional

What examples of resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making have you experienced?

How do we address resistances? Stage 1

- Identify the resistance
- Categorise – why, how, who
- Acknowledge common reactions to this resistance
- Set objectives – what is the minimum acceptable outcome?

How do we address resistances? Stage 2

- Detail the techniques required to address this resistance (5 concrete Action Points)
- Clarify how easy/difficult to address vs how important
- *Repeat for all major resistances currently being experienced*
- Finally, prioritise resistances to be addressed

Why do resistances matter?

- Persistent blockages to implementation of gender equality policies and programmes
- Resistances useful for understanding challenges and opportunities for institutional culture shift
- Engaging with resistances is essential for a gender-transformative approach

Discussion

Wrap-up and Conclusions

Annex 8: Presentation used in the first closed webinar

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Webinar: “Exploring bias and resistances to
gender equality in leadership and decision-
making in partner organisations”

Presentation Date: 12th June 2020

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 programme,
under grant agreement no. 824536

- **Maria Lopez Bellosso, GEARING Roles**
- **Lucy Ferguson, Yellow Window**

6 GEPs

GEP COUNTRIES - UK, Portugal, Spain, Slovenia, Turkey, Estonia

- ✓ Identify bias in leadership and decision decision-making in partner organisations
- ✓ Identify resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making in partner organisations
- ✓ Explore strategies for tackling bias and resistances

POLL 1

Do you think there is bias in leadership and decision-making in your institution?

What makes a good leader?

Using the Whiteboard facility, please describe the qualities of a good leader.

What does a leader look like?

Please take a couple of minutes to search for an image on the internet of a leader and send it via the chat facility.

QUIZ (VIA POLL QUESTIONS)

1. What is the proportion of women heads of institutions in the higher education sector across the EU?

A. 36%

B. 22 %

C. 15%

2. What proportion of board members of research organisations are women?

A. 27%

B. 40%

C. 18%

QUIZ (VIA POLL QUESTIONS)

3. What percentage of advisory group members are women?

A. 50%

B. 23%

C. 42%

4. What is the proportion of women members of evaluation panels?

A. 44%

B. 36%

C. 28%

What do we expect from a leader in research and innovation?

Can you think of any ways in which gender relates to these?

- Credentials and achievements
- Dedication and commitment
- Leadership skills
- Career progression pattern

Can you think of any ways in which gender relates to these?

- Formal selection processes
- Informal decision-making practices
- Peer selections and networking

Why does this matter?

Leadership and decision-making positions, bodies and practices are instances where “institutionalized gender bias” tends to be reproduced, if not effectively challenged.

Can you think of examples of measures that have been put in place to address any of the examples of gender bias discussed? Please share your experiences in the chat facility or by raising your hand.

10:30

POLL 2

Do you think there are resistances to implementing gender equality measures in leadership and decision-making in your institution?

What are resistances?

- Challenges and blockages to the implementation of gender equality policies and programmes
- Evidence of the gender-biased structures and practices of research institutions
- A necessary part of change

How can we understand resistances?

- **Why?** Specific resistance to gender equality or other issues
- **How?** Active/explicit, passive/implicit
- **Who?** Individual, group, institutional

Instructions for Group Discussion

- One person will be assigned as rapporteur for each group
- The rapporteur will record the discussions in the Google Doc provided. Feel free to include images or links to websites/videos
- In your breakout room, please introduce yourselves in turn, then discuss the questions provided
- We will then return to the full group and the rapporteurs will summarise the discussions

Discussion Questions (see Google Doc)

- Please list any examples of resistances to increasing gender equality in leadership and decision-making you can identify in your organisation
- Why do you think these resistances exist?
- What could be done to address these resistances?

11:00

Feedback from Group 1

Feedback from Group 2

POLL 3

Do you think there is bias in leadership and decision-making in your institution?

POLL 4

Do you think there are resistances to implementing gender equality measures in leadership and decision-making in your institution?

Wrap-up, Feedback and Conclusions

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1mntpk-d4BBb58ECJppPqP3qniWTTsNusXIXdd2Rb0pE/edit>

FURTHER RESOURCES

[She Figures 2018](https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en)

https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

[GEECCO project \(decision-making\)](http://www.geecco-project.eu/fileadmin/t/geecco/D4.1Gender_analysis_of_decision_making_bodies.pdf)

[http://www.geecco-project.eu/fileadmin/t/geecco/D4.1Gender analysis of decision making bodies .pdf](http://www.geecco-project.eu/fileadmin/t/geecco/D4.1Gender_analysis_of_decision_making_bodies.pdf)

[FESTA project \(resistances\)](https://www.festa-europa.eu/sites/festa-europa.eu/files/FESTA%20D7.1%20Handbook%20on%20Resistance%20to%20Gender%20Equality%20in%20Academia.pdf)

<https://www.festa-europa.eu/sites/festa-europa.eu/files/FESTA%20D7.1%20Handbook%20on%20Resistance%20to%20Gender%20Equality%20in%20Academia.pdf>

Annex 9: Presentation used in the second open webinar

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Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

GE Academy Webinars' series
**“Challenges for feminist leadership in Higher
Education Institutions”**
Joint webinar with Gearing Roles

Wednesday, 30 September 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

The challenge

There are many gender equality programmes, projects and a great gained knowledge

- **Gender analysis** remains rarely appropriated **within research projects**
- **Large differences** among research performing organisations **in various countries**
- **Small proportion of researchers and practitioners** are familiar with theoretical and methodological concepts of gender and feminist scholarship

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

The project

GE Academy, an Horizon 2020 project, which develops and implements a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in Research and Innovation (R&I) & Higher Education (HE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

Training offer

In-person training sessions

Interactive participatory workshops

Interactive webinars

Summer Schools

Train the Trainers session

Open Collaborative Online Course (DOCC)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

Partnership

- Strong experience in coordination and management of all partners
- Excellent experience in developing training methods and materials and in executing trainings
- Stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exploitation and communication excellent experience
- Institutional change experience of many partners
- Adaptability, flexibility, resilience and commitment

YouTube channel: Gender Equality Academy EU

Search

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49 views • 5 months ago

GE ACADEMY Webinars' Series: Introduction to...
209 views • 5 months ago

Coming up this October

Open calls

Online Training with ESF
Gender bias in recruitment, promotion and career management
| 14 October 2020

[REGISTER](#)

Webinar
Gender bias in academic recruitment and promotion.
Recognizing and overcoming it | 29 October 2020

[REGISTER \(COMING SOON\)](#)

Challenges for feminist leadership in Higher Education Institutions

Time	Topic
10.00-10.10	Vasia Madesi , ViLabs - GE ACADEMY coordinator & Maria Lopez Beloso , Deusto University, GEARING ROLES Introduction to the projects' goals and objectives and to the webinar
10.10-10.50	Talk by Fiona Mackay , University of Edinburgh, on feminist leadership in Academia
10.50-11.00	Reflections and reactions by Marloes Van Engen , discussant, Tilburg University (TBC)
11.00-11.20	Q&A session
11.20-11.30	Maria Lopez Beloso - Wrap up and conclusions

Thank you for the attention

We are live-tweeting, JOIN US with your impressions!

 @GEAcademy_eu

 @GEAcademy.eu

 GE Academy

 <https://ge-academy.eu/>

 info@ge-academy.eu

Vasia Madesi
Project Manager
Vilabs, Greece

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

Outsiders within? Dilemmas
of an academic feminist as
manager in the neo-liberal
Academy

- ▶ PROFESSOR FIONA MACKAY
- ▶ UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH
- ▶ F.S.MACKAY@ED.AC.UK
- ▶ @GENDERPOL @UOE_GENDERED

Questions

- ▶ What can feminists do when they take on management roles?
- ▶ How do feminists-who-manage experience simultaneously embodying institutional authority and oppositional knowledge?
- ▶ To what extent are there opportunities to work with the grain of an institution to challenge the gendered status quo from within?
- ▶ Are feminists-who-manage inevitably co-opted and compromised?

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2VCs on ... are women academics blocked from the top?

There are more women in UK universities than ever before, yet they're still outnumbered by men in leadership positions. What needs to change?

zackerley
017

▲ Valerie Ames and Shearer West. Illustration: Sophie Wolfson

Room at
the top?

Context: Management & Gender in HE

- ▶ Structural & Cultural Barriers persist
- ▶ Homosocial networks & practices
- ▶ Gendered division of labour
- ▶ “Gender Devaluation” (Monroe et al 2008)
- ▶ Personal & Professional Costs
- ▶ Ambition, Agency, pleasure
- ▶ Why so few studies of **feminist** managers?

Context: the Neo Liberal Academy

My 'story'

- ▶ **Feminist political scientist:** political representation, political institutions, institutional and policy change
- ▶ **An “accidental” academic:** adult returner, former journalist, one-time single parent.
- ▶ 1998: 1st permanent job in academia (aged 39); 2003: Senior Lecturer (Assoc Prof); 2012: Personal Chair
- ▶ From **“accidental” to “proactive leader”**: Deputy Director (2003-7) then Director (2009-12) Graduate School of Social Sciences, Dean & Head of School of Social and Political Science (2014-2017), founding Director genderED (2017-)

What's the role?

- ▶ “the role of Head of School (Executive Dean) occupies a central position in the leadership structure of the University”
- ▶ Budgets
- ▶ People
- ▶ Resources
- ▶ Strategy and Planning

Surviving Sexism in Academia
LEADERSHIP

Managing like a Man? Managing like a feminist?
Managing like a Tempered Radical

Four Lessons

- ▶ **Lesson 1:** Everyday feminism and academic management
- ▶ **Lesson 2:** Institutional readiness – “Seizing the moment”
- ▶ **Lesson 3:** ... sometimes you’re just “The Man”
- ▶ **Lesson 4:** Feminist manager as gender stereotype: “It took a woman”

1. Everyday Feminism

- ▶ “Nudging” organizational change
- ▶ Recognising and rewarding different academic models
- ▶ Equalities work is for everyone
- ▶ Mitigating /interpreting measurement and performance frameworks through a feminist lens
- ▶ “Small wins” (within wider constraints)

genderED // showcasing gender and sexualities studies at the University of Edinburgh and beyond

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Standalone genderED blog
Explore our current projects and collaborations

www.gender.ed.ac.uk

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
School of Social
& Political Science

2. Seizing the Moment

3. Academic Feminist Manager as "The Man"

4. It took a woman ...

A few take-homes

- ▶ Chipping Away
- ▶ Seizing the moment
- ▶ Recognising limits and divided loyalties
- ▶ Ongoing power of stereotypes
- ▶ Where do feminists and their allies need to be? Everywhere!

- ▶ Thanks!

Annex 10: Presentation used in the second closed webinar

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research
Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Webinar: “Exploring Challenges to Leadership in
Research and Higher Education”

Presentation Date: 21st October 2020, 10.30am-
12.00pm CET

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 programme,
under grant agreement no. 824536

- **Maria Silvestre Cabrera, GEARING Roles**
- **Lucy Ferguson, Yellow Window**

- ✓ Discuss key issues and challenges for leaders in research and higher education institutions
- ✓ Explore the concept of “feminist leadership”
- ✓ Review leadership targets in a Gender Equality Plan

- ✓ Fourth and final webinar in the series
- ✓ 1 and 3 available online
- ✓ Follow up on previous closed session

Examples of resistances

- Belief that equality has already been achieved
- Meritocracy discourse
- Resistances to go through an external evaluation or to show/share the results of the evaluation
- Unable to see gender imbalances or to consider them as a problem
- Perception that work is done with 60% women in workforce
- Lack of awareness (unconscious bias)

- We want to incorporate the flag of equality (diversity) but without challenging previous structures (because we were supposed to be already very “progressive”)
- Institutional changes challenge the typical hierarchy structure
- Not seeing the ‘business case’ and mainstream business improvement - especially in time of crisis
- Not enough awareness or knowledge of what gender equality really means and the benefits it entails for everyone in an organisation (not just women)
- Too many priorities, worries, too much on our plate; and this comes down in the priority list

Causes of resistances (continued)

- Patriarchal ideology: belief that the claim is ideological
- Women leaders fear perception of tokenism and reduction in 'quality'
- Middle-class and white liberal discourse - resistant to risk for non-typical progression routes /experience
- We believe we are fair!
- Requests for more and more and more DATA
- Gender equality and race/ethnicity action seen as separate - intersectional issues not understood
- Gender fatigue - it is always the same people addressing these topics

Suggestions for dealing with resistances

- Show gender equality as a benefit for the future of the whole organisation
- Enable open discussion
- Delivery of Gender Equality Plans and regular assessment
- Importance of involving top-management leaders and to make them aware of the benefits of gender equality for the institution
- Changing socio-cultural values and beliefs, so more actions and discussions are needed
- Positive action for recognition of gender and other identities and experience
- Do not perpetuate care duties as female duties

POLL 1

Do you consider the challenges for leaders in research and higher education to be the same for women and men?

Please tell us about a challenge you face in leadership in your institution using the video.

Do you consider this to be connected to gender issues?

11:05

1. What is a feminist style of leadership?

Minimum: social justice, inclusion, self-reflection...(horizontal, diverse)

2. Do you want to be a feminist leader?

Commitment vs. Threat (ideology)

3. Is feminist leadership connected to organizational change?
Structural change / Radical change (WITH Org. commitment;
Tempered radicals)

4. Feminist Leadership vs. Female Leadership?
Female vs. Feminine Advantage

POLL 2

Do you consider yourself to be a feminist leader?

Please share your answer with the group using the video,
and explain why/why not.

11:25

Leadership in the University of Deusto GEP, Maria López, Deusto

Building in the results of the diagnosis:

Data:

“Power structures are male dominated at the highest level (Governing Council, Board of Directors and Rectorate), and parity is achieved in greater proportion at intermediate Levels (Departments’ Management, Vice-Deans' Offices and Unit Directorates), where the presence of women is very notable.”

Graph 2: Sex composition of management bodies

Leadership in the University of Deusto GEP, Maria López, Deusto

Building in the results of the diagnosis:

Perceptions:

In general, the members of the Board of Directors who were interviewed showed **no awareness of inequality situations**; the majority believe that women and men occupy decision-making positions equally at our university and that there is no discrimination.

When asked the specific question of whether women have particular difficulty accessing positions of power and decision-making, the general opinion is that **women encounter no additional difficulties to reach leadership positions because they are women**. In this respect, it was stated several times that men receive no preferential treatment for access, promotion, or remuneration in decision-making positions. It was also noted that evaluation, assessment and performance criteria for all candidates are the same, thus highlighting the absolute neutrality.

Main objective GEP: to increase awareness of the need to implement measures for effective equality at the University of Deusto and to ensure compliance with the principle of equality between women and men

Gearing Roles specific objectives regarding leadership:

Deusto's GEP objectives regarding leadership:

Encourage equal representation and participation in leadership and decision making

SG 5.1: Promote equal representation in decision-making bodies

Analyse and redefine leadership model from a gender perspective

SG 5.2: Promote behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership styles.

Support awareness raising and behavioral changes towards inclusive leadership

SG 5.3: Analyse and propose improvements in the institution's leadership model from a gender perspective.

Promote equal representation in decision-making bodies

SG5: LEADERSHIP

SG 5.1: Promote equal representation in decision-making bodies

Measure 18. Prioritise the promotion of women in those areas, positions and job categories where female leadership is less or non-existent

Action 40. M18. Include specific scores in the evaluation of candidates, based on the representativeness of the gender to which they belong in the body to which they aspire

Promote behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership styles.

Measure 19. Design and implement a training program for the people who exercise leadership in the institution

Action 41. M19. Design specific training actions within the UD training offer, which are compulsory for those people who access / are in management positions

Measure 20. Analyse the specific problems of conciliation and overload of work of women who assume responsibilities at the University

Action 42. M20. Implement a questionnaire to all UD workers with specific questions about the leadership observed **(GR)**

Measure 21: Develop a training program for the people who exercise leadership in the institution: training session for the board of directors and participation of two people in the training course for women leaders

Action 43. M21. Conduct a training and awareness session with the Board of Directors **(GR)**; Action 44. M21. Participate in the Training Program for Women Leaders developed by Yellow Window (YW) in the framework of the GEARING-Roles Project **(GR)**; Action 45. M21. Design specific webinars on leadership and encourage the participation of senior managers of the UD **(GR)**

→ Gearing Roles survey on Leadership

→ Session with Board of Directors-Awareness raising

→ Webinars for leaders

→ Training for current and potential female leaders

Analyse and propose improvements in the institution's leadership model from a gender perspective

Measure 22. Analyse the leadership model and make proposals for its improvement

Action 46. M22. Carry out group reflection sessions about the leadership model of the institution in the different groups of the UD

Action 47. M22. Apply a questionnaire to all UD staff with specific questions about the leadership observed (GR)

In depth interviews-GAP Analysis

Gearing Roles survey on Leadership

Gearing Roles KPIs regarding Leadership

- (1) 10% Increase the representation of women in decision making bodies in relation with baseline assessment at different ranks;
- (2) 6 action plans developed with elements to include leadership and female participation in decision making;
- (3) data collection on increase awareness;
- (4) number of questionnaires contrasting data in relation to baseline assessment.

<i>OBJETIVES</i>	<i>MEASURES</i>	<i>ACTIONS</i>	<i>INDICATORS</i>	<i>RESPONSIBILITIES</i>
SG 5.1: Promote equal representation in decision-making bodies	M.18. Prioritise the promotion of women in those areas, positions and job categories where female leadership is less or non-existent	A.40. Include specific scores in the evaluation of candidates, based on the representativeness of the gender to which they belong in the body to which they aspire	Deployment of the action: Criteria set? (yes/no) As a result: Recent promotions take into account the move towards higher levels of balanced representation.	Board of Directors People Management Teaching Staff Committee

<i>OBJETIVES</i>	<i>MEASURES</i>	<i>ACTIONS</i>	<i>INDICATORS</i>	<i>RESPONSIBILITIES</i>
<p>SG 5.2: Promote behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership styles</p>	<p>M.19. Design and implement a training program for the people who exercise leadership in the institution</p>	<p>A.41. Design specific training actions within the UD training offer, which are compulsory for those people who access / are in management positions</p>	<p>Deployment of the action: Number of training programs deployed Attendants to training programmes</p>	<p>Personal Management (Development)</p>

<i>OBJETIVES</i>	<i>MEASURES</i>	<i>ACTIONS</i>	<i>INDICATORS</i>	<i>RESPONSIBILITIES</i>
<p>SG 5.2: Promote behavioural changes towards inclusive leadership styles</p>	<p>M.19. Design and implement a training program for the people who exercise leadership in the institution</p>	<p>A.41. Design specific training actions within the UD training offer, which are compulsory for those people who access / are in management positions</p>	<p>Deployment of the action: Number of training programs deployed Attendants to training programmes</p>	<p>Personal Management (Development)</p>

Leadership in the University of Deusto GEP

<p>M.20. Analyse the specific problems of conciliation and overload of work of women who assume responsibilities at the University</p>	<p>A.42. Implement a questionnaire to all UD workers with specific questions about the leadership observed (GR)</p>	<p>Number of replies to the questionnaire</p>	<p>GR CPI</p>
<p>M.21. Develop a training program for the people who exercise leadership in the institution: training session for the board of directors and participation of two people in the training course for women leaders</p>	<p>A.43. Conduct a training and awareness session with the Board of Directors (GR)</p>	<p>Implementation of the proposed actions Training attendance ratio</p>	<p>GR</p>
	<p>A.44. Participate in the Training Program for Women Leaders developed by Yellow Window (YW) in the framework of the GEARING-Roles Project (GR)</p>	<p>Implementation of the proposed actions Training attendance ratio</p>	<p>GR</p>
	<p>A.45. Design specific webinars on leadership and encourage the participation of senior managers of the UD (GR)</p>	<p>Implementation of the proposed actions Training attendance ratio</p>	<p>GR</p>

SG 5.3: Analyse and propose improvements in the institution's leadership model from a gender perspective	M.22. Analyse the leadership model and make proposals for its improvement	A.46. Carry out group reflection sessions about the leadership model of the institution in the different groups of the UD	Number of focus groups conducted	USR
		A.47. Apply a questionnaire to all UD staff with specific questions about the leadership observed (GR)	Number of responses to questionnaire QUALITATIVES: Characteristic features of the institution's leadership identified Proposals for improvement made	USR-equality GR

11:50

Wrap-up, Feedback and Conclusions

<https://forms.gle/n2Xc9A3TrEd224Xc7>

FURTHER RESOURCES

Videos

Podcast

<https://gearingroles.eu/outputs/>

**Best practices in leadership and
decision-making**

<https://gearingroles.eu/wp5/>

Annex 11: Presentation used in the Leadership Training

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GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research
Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-
making

SESSION 1 - DATA AND DEFINITIONS

Wednesday 18th November 2020, 9.30-11am

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 programme,
under grant agreement no. 824536

María López Beloso, GEARING ROLES

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeNdVLPVJvj7A7wEG9ujjRCyELTFuhGKVZ6SoC4s00jJcibeg/viewform>

Fernanda Campanini, predoctoral researcher and
Research Assistant GEARING ROLES (observer)

Trainer

**Lucy Ferguson,
Yellow Window**

POLL

**How are you feeling
today?**

Participant introductions

- Patricia Abrantes, auxiliary professor since 2018, and researcher. Interests on GIS, spatial modelling and urban planning. Mom of two little girls.
- Ana Estevens, was PI of one research project
- Katielle Silva, leads with another woman, an editorial team for a scientific journal in Brazil.

- Hulya Adak, Gender Director
- Mutlu Bozkurt Besimzade, Marketing and Institutional Director
- Idil Seker, Human Resources Director
- Selmiye Alkan Gürsel, Vice Dean of Research
- Huriye Pandul, CFO. Previously Finance Director in leading Energy Company in Turkey.

- Charoula Tzanakou, Senior Research Fellow, ‘leadership’ experience of being the social scientist lead in an EU consortium, leading research network
- Anne Laure Humbert, Reader in Gender and Diversity, Director of the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice

- Liina Eek, Programme manager in Estonian Research Council for 5 years. Before that worked in Ministry of Environment and UNEP.
- Karin Jaanson, worked as a leader for 20 years. 5 years in my current position
- Maarja Adojaan, Head of Department in Estonian Research Council

- Rosa María Santibañez, Vice Rector for Research and Transfer, Chair professor of Psychology & Education Faculty
- Cristina Diago, Head of Human Resources. Working as a Human Resources Manager for last 20 years in several organizations.
- Gema Tomas, Dean of the Law Faculty, First woman in the position, Chair professor of private Law
- Eider Landaberea, Secretary General

Expectations for the training (1)

“I would like to train myself and be able to better train trainers.”

“Learning about the experiences of others always helps”

“I rely on intuition; I do not know how other leaders work; perhaps I could use techniques that I am not aware of”

“I will know as I start with it may empower me in networking, prioritizing and reaching people...”

“For sure, it would help me to have more self consciousness and to improve some skills”

“A chance to reflect and share experiences”

Expectations for the training (2)

“Every time I listen about leadership I learn different and new ideas”

“Improve guidance”

“More formal training, I learnt largely on the job or via anti-role models”

“Help me to analyse my strengths/weaknesses and help to better manage leadership situations in multi gender teams.”

“Providing knowledge about other leadership experiences”

“Reflecting more on my leadership and understand how I could further improve my practice for managing diversity successfully in the organization”

“For managing diversity successfully in the organization”

- ✓ Critically analyse the gender dimensions of leadership and decision-making
- ✓ Understand gender stereotypes related to leadership and decision-making and explore how these can be challenged
- ✓ Identify common biases and resistances women may experience in leadership – at the individual and institutional level - and find ways to address these
- ✓ Develop skills and networks for leadership for structural change

Session 1, 9.30-11am: Data and Definitions

Session 2, 11.30am-1pm: Challenges, biases and resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision-making

Session 3, 9.30am-11am: Building skills and confidence to meet challenges

Session 4, 11.30am-1pm: Panel: women leaders in higher education

Session 5, 9.30am-11am: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

Session 1: Data and Definitions

QUIZ:

Statistics on gender equality in leadership and decision-making in partner organisations

VISUAL ACTIVITY:

What does a university leader look like?

Please search for an image online of what a typical senior leader in a university looks like, and share it in the chat

10:15

Instructions for Group Discussion

- Please assign one person as rapporteur for each group
- The rapporteur will record the discussions in the Google Doc provided. Feel free to include images or links to websites/videos
- In your breakout room, please discuss the questions provided
- We will then return to the full group and the rapporteurs will summarise the discussions (10.45)

Group Activity: Leadership strengths and weaknesses

Group 1 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nFIJfwSy4Jw4nPWt4RNOC7ipqdgvn-ye/view?usp=sharing>

Group 2

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1q4bn_jewGeMc21avWRiDFobrRSc74kCR/view?usp=sharing

Group 3

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xchFB406HZ_2R5dVHvXQihq1fnuWK6Ge/view?usp=sharing

Group 4

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1uVSpWuQERUfg5r_IVn0vaU7P2SMBCv7I/view?usp=sharing

Group feedback

11:00-11.30
BREAK

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions
to transform Gender Roles

Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-making
SESSION 2 - CHALLENGES, BIASES AND
RESISTANCE TO GENDER EQUALITY IN
LEADERSHIP AND DECISION-MAKING
Wednesday 18th November 2020, 11.30am-1pm

This project has received funding from the
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REFLECTION: WOMEN'S LEADERSHIP IN THE COVID19 RESPONSE

<https://ideas.ted.com/6-things-we-can-learn-from-how-women-leaders-have-handled-the-pandemic/>

<https://moderndiplomacy.eu/2020/10/16/coronavirus-and-the-female-leaders-of-the-world/>

“Empathy and decisiveness are the two key traits that have allowed female leaders to succeed through the coronavirus crisis. Empathy allows these leaders to quickly grasp the severity of the situation, while timely decision-making means action is taken quickly. Rosabeth Moss Kanter, professor of business at Harvard Business School remarks, “Women don’t have a monopoly on these skills, but they might be less likely to let their egos get in the way, or play politics with the crisis.”

“The leadership qualities and values shown by the female leaders have the potential to change the perception of leadership itself. This could shape the leadership in future especially with the new challenges coming ahead due to climate change.”

“Wittenberg-Cox has identified four common threads in women’s leadership during the pandemic: trust, decisiveness, tech, love.”

“She emphasizes that good leaders from both genders all used the first three (trust, decisiveness, tech), but the fourth factor — love — is what really set the women apart. “What I found very interesting is these women were much more ready and comfortable expressing love and care while leading,” she says.”

- Do women have natural characteristics that make them better leaders?
- What is the role of “love” in leadership?
- Is this kind of argument helpful?

12:00

Session 2: Challenges, biases and resistances to gender equality in leadership and decision- making

- Gendered norms around “effective” leadership
- Leadership styles
- Communication skills
- Negotiation skills
- Networking skills
- “Strengths” and “weaknesses” discussed in previous session

- The role of care work - domestic, community
- “Academic care work”
- Institutional culture
- Formal and informal decision-making
- Institutional gender bias
- Institutional resistances

Group 1 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1EgLa2gaP3H1nPesuLxSKY-kISpN9S0wL/view?usp=sharing>

Group 2

https://drive.google.com/file/d/12bl8LNBbiUHCY_hpfZkIY60aQc84YkR/view?usp=sharing

Group 3

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rrWkxSzbBFjtHtg2EmUHYXtYIlg58nCFB/view?usp=sharing>

12:45

Group feedback

- Reflections Day 1
- Request for volunteers role play

1PM CLOSE

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research
Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-
making

SESSION 3 - Building skills and confidence to
meet challenges

Thursday 19th November 2020, 9.30-11am

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Session 3: Building skills and confidence to meet challenges

Reflections on Day 1...

POLL:

Leadership ambitions....

- Already received questions
- Please send any further questions based on reflections to date

Activity: Leadership Role Plays

- Please think about a concrete scenario in which you would have liked to act differently and have a different outcome
- Feeling not taken seriously as young and different nationality - what is the concrete scenario?
- Unable to turn down “care work” or additional work - what is the concrete scenario?

- Identify a common leadership challenge
- Agree on the setting and distribute roles
- Play out the “worst case scenario” for this challenge

- For “actors” - how did you feel in this role? What could you have done differently?
- For observers - what could each character have done differently (individual/personal?)
- For all - what could have been done differently to change the setting and the outcome? (institutional)

10:30

POLL:

Do you feel more confident in dealing with leadership challenges than before the training?

Review: Expectations and Concerns

Revisit: What
does a
university leader
look like?

Presenters:

- Christine MUSSELIN, CNRS Research Professor, Centre de Sociologie des Organisations, Sciences Po - CNRS
- Fiona Mackay FAcSS, FRSE, Professor of Politics, School of Social and Political Science, University of Edinburgh
- Gemma Irvine, Vice-President for Equality & Diversity, Maynooth University

- Q&A session from the participants

11-11.30am
BREAK

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research
Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-
making

SESSION 4 - Panel: women leaders in higher
education

Thursday 19th November 2020, 11.30am-1pm

This project has received funding from the
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Session 4: Panel: Women Leaders in Higher Education

Christine Musselein

Christine MUSSELIN, CNRS Research
Professor, Centre de Sociologie des
Organisations, Sciences Po - CNRS

Fiona MacKay

Fiona Mackay FAcSS, FRSE, Professor
of Politics, School of Social and
Political Science, University of
Edinburgh

Gemma Irvine

Gemma Irvine, Vice-President for
Equality & Diversity, Maynooth
University

12.15

Q&A Session

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fxe7KrqahjQvxOjf-95eJiYOw3gEx1Gh/view?usp=sharing>

- “How were you able to manage/achieve work/life balance?”
- “How do you deal with resilience, career-management, and self-care?”
- “What kind of gender bias have you suffered from being a woman and holding a decision-making position?”

- “How do you manage upwards? (how do you manage more senior people than you)?”
- “What would you advise, how to behave if you are treated as empty place just because of being female, especially by elderly men in higher positions? Do you have any good tricks how to become visible if you do not have strong voice and if you do not want to become aggressive, but would prefer to stay calm?”

- Present the Action Plan to allow participants to reflect briefly and make some notes overnight

1pm
CLOSE

GEARING ROLES

Gender Equality Actions in Research
Institutions to transform Gender Roles

Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-
making
SESSION 5 - Action Plans for Gender Equality in
Leadership and Decision-Making
Friday 20th November 2020, 9.30-11am

This project has received funding from the
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“How are you
feeling this
morning?”

“What is the main message you take with you into the final day of this workshop?”

Session 5: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision- Making

Activity: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

- Working in groups with colleagues from own institution
- At the end of the exercise, each team should have a rough draft of an action plan - at the individual and the institutional level
- These will be developed further in the in-person training at Deusto in June 2021

Activity: Action Plans for Gender Equality in Leadership and Decision-Making

- Group 1 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1MSuXWk6jggjohdUqU3DN-8cMV-HsYI3R/view?usp=sharing>
- Group 2 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BsU7b90Y4jVvuqkVvyaZ39Vgk63y0Z1V/view?usp=sharing>
- Group 3 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iVBrmDpC3eoqdZk7vpP2YhzVjXPxUXs/view?usp=sharing>

10.15

Group

feedback

POLL

Leadership ambitions (revisited)

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iVBrmDpC3eoqdZk7vpP2YhzVjXPxUX_s/view?usp=sharing

- Exit Questionnaire

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1AqALHBBIPoKk-DBEGKx_Q3c-fyFbX1SajCDmmfX57oA/edit

- Follow up session June 2021
- Final reflections....

11am
CLOSE

Annex 12: Evaluation of the Leadership Programme

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EVALUATION OF THE TRAINING PROGRAMME

9 participants completed the exit questionnaire, with the key results indicated below:

How satisfied are you with the relevance of the workshop for your own work?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the relevance of the workshop for your own professional career?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the content of the workshop?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the methodology of the workshop?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the length of the workshop?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the facilitator's knowledge of the subject?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the facilitator's communication skills?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the facilitator's relation with the group?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the support and advice offered to participants by the facilitator?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the selection of activities and group work?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the visual supports?

9 responses

How satisfied are you with the balance between theory and practice?

9 responses

To what extent did the workshop meet its first objective - critically analyse the gender dimensions of leadership and decision-making?

9 responses

To what extent did the workshop meet its second objective - understand gender stereotypes related to leadership and decision-making and explore how these can be challenged ?

9 responses

To what extent did the workshop meet its third objective - identify common biases and resistances women may experience in leadership at the individual and institutional level and find ways to address these?

9 responses

To what extent did the workshop meet its fourth objective - develop skills and networks for leadership for structural change?

9 responses

Overall, how satisfied are you with this workshop?

9 responses

Would you be interested in further online sessions to develop the ideas and skills learned in this training?

9 responses

In terms of further sessions, participants highlighted:

- Analysis of concrete examples from participants' leading experience. Role plays and their analysis.
- Both the presentations were very inspirational as well as activities.
- Practical session on specific skills: dealing with conflict, assertiveness.
- It would be better to figure out "understanding self potential and appreciation".

In terms of what they found most interesting, participants highlighted the role play, learning from each others' experiences, and the panel presentations.

Participants expected to apply the contents of the training in the following ways:

- I will try to strategically develop my skills as a leader.
- I hope that I would be able to apply them to my daily life.
- Slowly and surely :)
- I plan to unite with other participants in our University and come up with an action plan.
- I will try. The networking.

A number of points were highlighted that could prevent participants from using the acquired knowledge:

- My personality
- Lack of time to constantly think about improving my leadership skills
- To avoid burning out
- That I am not a current leader
- Fast mind shift takes time
- Workload

Participants felt less confident about:

- To cope with problems
- It seems I need more ambition :)
- My own strengths
- Some of the exercises were superficially addressed
- Cost of saying "no" in order to balance career management and self care
- Being alone in implementing what I learned

- Structural change

They would like to know more about:

- Strategies of being a good leader
- Practical examples and analysis of the situations
- Leadership skills, personal experiences from leaders
- Career planning
- More on how to develop actions to help organisations to change in how they perceive leadership
- How to gain male leadership styles?
- Focus on other competencies like saying NO
- Develop skills and networks for leadership for structural change

The main points learned in the workshop were:

- Challenges of leadership
- We do not have to be like men leaders. We have our strengths.
- Everyone has the same challenges in this way
- That we need to be more confident and remove our own stereotypes
- Liked the microaggressions that Gemma Irvine presented and the theoretical concepts used by Fiona Mackay.
- Gender specific strengths and weaknesses is not a destiny, we can change & redirect for good. I need to focus more on what to do/actions.
- Women need to be courageous to step up for upper roles and do not wait to be perfect.
- The need to seek support before submitting new proposals to a management team